

Multiple zeta values with classical applications

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Foreword

The goal of this exposition is to introduce theory of colored multiple zeta values (CMZVs), with emphasis on some classical problems, such as integral/series evaluations in a systematic and mechanical way.

Before the introduction of this systematic approach, many of such evaluations are investigated on an *ad hoc* basis. It is the author's humble opinion that only it could reveal the true nature of these integrals, while simultaneously pointing to far-reaching generalizations which are not quite do-able via elementary means.

I tried to minimize the prerequisites on reading these articles. Doubtlessly, one must possess enough mathematical maturity in order to understand what is going on.

Throughout, I will frequently refer to examples that are generated by the Mathematica package `MultipleZetaValues`. Many of functions therein will be elaborated as we go along.

This note is still under construction, further chapters are pending.

Chapter 0

Introductory examples with definite integrals

In this chapter, we give some motivation for upcoming chapters. The treatment will be informal and we will not prove anything. Readers don't need motivations can go directly to next chapter.

0.1 Level and weight

Let N be a positive integer, $\Gamma_N \subset \mathbb{C}$ be the set of N -th roots of unity. A rational function $R(x)$ is called N -unital if zeroes and poles of both R and $1 - R$ are contained in $\Gamma_N \cup \{0\}$.

Example 0.1.1. $R(x) = (2x)/(1+x)^2$ is 4-unital, because poles of R is $x = -1$, zeroes of R is $x = 0$, poles of $1 - R$ is $x = \pm i$, all these numbers are in $\Gamma_4 \cup \{0\}$.

Exercise 0.1.2. (a) Show that all 1-unital functions are given by $\{x, 1-x, 1/x, 1-1/x, x/(x-1), 1/(1-x)\}$.
(b) Show that the following functions are 4-unital:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)(x+1)}{x+i}, \frac{4x}{(x+1)^2}, \frac{(1-i)x^2 + 2x + (1+i)}{4x}$$

It can be shown, for a given N , there are only finitely many N -unital functions. The proof is non-trivial and we will not use it.

Let R_1, \dots, R_k be N -unital functions, n_i be positive integers, $a \in \Gamma_N \cup \{0\}$, consider the integral

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{n_1}(R_1(x)) \cdots \text{Li}_{n_k}(R_k(x))}{x-a} dx \tag{1}$$

N is called its level, $n_1 + \dots + n_k + 1$ is called its weight. Note that $\text{Li}_1(x) = -\log(1-x)$, so the definition also allows presence of $\log(R(x))$. This represents a very general class of integral, some of its special cases are:

Example 0.1.3.

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^{n_1}(x) \log^{n_2}(1-x) \text{Li}_{n_3}(x)^{b_1}}{x} dx$$

has level 1 and weight $n_1 + n_2 + b_1 n_3 + 1$.

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^{n_1}(x) \log^{n_2}(1-x) \log^{n_3}(1+x)}{x-a} dx \quad a \in \{0, 1, -1\}$$

has level 2 and weight $n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + 1$. Because $\arctan x = \frac{i}{2} [\log(1-ix) - \log(1+ix)]$, and $1 \pm ix$ are 4-unital functions, so $\int_0^1 \frac{\arctan x}{x} dx$ has level 4 and weight 2,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x \arctan x \log(1+x^2)}{x^2+1} dx$$

has level 4 and weight 3,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log x \log(1+x^2) \text{Li}_2\left(\frac{2x}{(1+x)^2}\right)}{1-x} dx$$

has level 4 and weight 5.

Among different levels N , those with $N = 1, 2, 4$ are most frequently discussed, due to presence of "nice" functions $\arctan x, \log(1+x^2), \log(1 \pm x)$. However, in our framework, all N 's can be treated on equal grounds:

Exercise 0.1.4. Show that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log(1-x) \log(x^2+x+1) \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}x}{x+2}\right)}{x} dx$$

has level 3 weight 4.

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log\left(\frac{1}{2}(x^2+1)\right) \arctan(x^2) \arctan(x)}{1-x} dx$$

has level 8 weight 4.

Remark 0.1.5. Not all possible integrals from formula (1) is convergent. Nonetheless, one can assign a "regularized value" to divergent integrals. More about this later, the theoretical details are non-trivial.

0.2 Dimension formula

Definition 0.2.1. : Let $V_{N,w}$ be the \mathbb{Q} -span of all convergent integrals

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{n_1}(R_1(x)) \cdots \text{Li}_{n_k}(R_k(x))}{x-a} dx$$

, with R_1, \dots, R_k ranges over all N -unital functions, n_i range over positive integers with $w = n_1 + \dots + n_k + 1$, $a \in \Gamma_N \cup \{0\}$.

Therefore $V_{N,w}$ is a vector space over \mathbb{Q} . The following result is extremely deep:

Theorem 0.2.2. *We have the following bounds on dimensions of $V_{N,w}$:*

- $\dim(\mathbb{R} \cap V_{1,n}) \leq a_n$, here a_n is defined recursively by

$$a_n = a_{n-2} + a_{n-3} \quad a_1 = 0, a_2 = 1, a_3 = 1$$

- $\dim(\mathbb{R} \cap V_{2,n}) \leq a_n$, here

$$a_n = a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} \quad a_1 = 1, a_2 = 2$$

which are Fibonacci's number.

- $\dim V_{3,n} \leq 2^n$, $\dim V_{4,n} \leq 2^n$, $\dim V_{8,n} \leq 3^n$

For many other N , there exist similar bounds. For small weight and level: the above bounds are conjectured to be tight, and $a \in V_{N,w_1}, b \in V_{N,w_2} \implies ab \in V_{N,w_1+w_2}$. We make this assumption in all our illustrations. Now we play a fun game of counting constants.

Example 0.2.3. Let $N = 2$, $V'_{2,n} = \mathbb{R} \cap V_{2,n}$, $\dim V'_{2,n} = 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21$ for $n = 1, \dots, 7$. Note that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{1+x} dx = \log 2 \implies \log 2 \in V'_{2,1} \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\log x}{1-x} dx = -\frac{\pi^2}{6}, \int_0^1 \frac{\log(x+1)}{1+x} dx = \frac{\log^2 2}{2} \implies \log^2 2, \pi^2 \in V'_{2,2}$$

so $V'_{2,1} = \mathbb{Q} \log 2$, $V'_{2,2} = \mathbb{Q} \log^2 2 + \mathbb{Q} \pi^2$, the theorem predicts $\dim V'_{2,3} = 3$, indeed, we have three real numbers that span the space $\{\log^3 2, \pi^2 \log 2, \zeta(3)\}$; similarly for $\dim V'_{2,4} = 5$, which are spanned by

$$\left\{ \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \zeta(3) \log(2), \pi^4, \pi^2 \log^2(2), \log^4(2) \right\}$$

similarly for $\dim V'_{2,5} = 8$, which are spanned by

$$\left\{ \zeta(5), \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \log(2), \pi^2 \zeta(3), \zeta(3) \log^2(2), \pi^4 \log(2), \pi^2 \log^3(2), \log^5(2) \right\}$$

For instance, $\int_0^1 \frac{\log(x+1)\log(1-x)\log^2(x)}{x+1} dx$ has weight 5 and level 2, so it is a rational combination of above 8 numbers, indeed, it equals

$$-8\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - 4\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2) - \frac{5\pi^2\zeta(3)}{12} + \frac{213\zeta(5)}{16} + \frac{7}{4}\zeta(3)\log^2(2) - \frac{1}{10}\log^5(2) + \frac{1}{18}\pi^2\log^3(2) - \frac{49}{720}\pi^4\log(2)$$

$\int_0^1 \frac{\log(1+x)\log(x)\text{Li}_2\left(\frac{1+x}{2}\right)}{1-x} dx$ has weight 5 and level 2, so it has a similar result

$$8\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + 7\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2) + \frac{7\pi^2\zeta(3)}{12} - \frac{437\zeta(5)}{32} + \frac{17}{8}\zeta(3)\log^2(2) + \frac{9\log^5(2)}{40} - \frac{5}{36}\pi^2\log^3(2) - \frac{1}{96}\pi^4\log(2)$$

Now we move on to weight 6, $\dim V'_{2,5} = 13$, using our familiar construction, we are only get 12 constants:

$$\left\{ \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \zeta(5)\log(2), \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2), \pi^2\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log^2(2), \zeta(3)^2, \right. \\ \left. \pi^2\zeta(3)\log(2), \zeta(3)\log^3(2), \pi^6, \pi^4\log^2(2), \pi^2\log^4(2), \log^6(2), ??? \right\}$$

Without elaborate machinery, it is very hard to get an elementary representation of this remaining constant.

It can be chosen to be either

$$\Re\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1+i}{2}\right) \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{243}\text{Li}_6\left(-\frac{1}{8}\right)$$

I will adopt the first choice. Then we can evaluate any level 2, weight 6 integrals in terms of above constants:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log(x)\log^2(1-x)\log^2(x+1)}{x} dx = -\frac{1024}{69}\Re\left(\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{632\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{69} + 4\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log^2(2) + 8\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2) \\ - \frac{25\zeta(3)^2}{16} + \frac{7}{6}\zeta(3)\log^3(2) - \frac{31}{8}\zeta(5)\log(2) + \frac{89\pi^6}{25920} + \frac{349\log^6(2)}{3105} - \frac{53}{621}\pi^2\log^4(2) + \frac{343\pi^4\log^2(2)}{49680}$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_2(-x)\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1-x}{2}\right)}{x+1} dx = \frac{1024}{23}\Re\left(\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{1}{3}\pi^2\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{218\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{23} + 2\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log^2(2) \\ + \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2) + \frac{35\zeta(3)^2}{64} + \frac{23}{48}\zeta(3)\log^3(2) - \frac{5}{16}\pi^2\zeta(3)\log(2) + \frac{287}{64}\zeta(5)\log(2) - \frac{2381\pi^6}{120960} + \frac{13\log^6(2)}{207} \\ - \frac{397\pi^2\log^4(2)}{6624} + \frac{533\pi^4\log^2(2)}{33120}$$

Example 0.2.4. Let $N = 4$. $\dim V'_{4,n} = 2, 4, 8, 16, 32$ for $n = 1, \dots, 5$. Note that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{x \pm i} dx = -\frac{\pm i\pi}{4} + \frac{\log 2}{2}$$

so $\{i\pi, \log 2\}$ span $V'_{4,1}$. One can show $\{(i\pi)^2, i\pi\log 2, \log^2 2, iG\}$ span $V'_{4,2}$, here G is Catalan's constant.

For weight 3, we need to adjoin two constants $\zeta(3), i\Im\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right)$ to reach the predicted 8 constants:

$$\left\{ \zeta(3), i\Im\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right), \pi G, iG\log(2), -i\pi^3, -\pi^2\log(2), i\pi\log^2(2), \log^3(2) \right\}$$

For weight 4, we need to adjoin $i\beta(4), \text{Li}_4(\frac{1}{2}), i\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right)$ to reach 16 constants:

$$\left\{ \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), i\beta(4), i\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right), i\pi\zeta(3), \zeta(3)\log(2), \pi\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right), \right. \\ \left. i\log(2)\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right), G^2, -i\pi^2G, \pi G\log(2), iG\log^2(2), \pi^4, -i\pi^3\log(2), -\pi^2\log^2(2), i\pi\log^3(2), \log^4(2) \right\}$$

All weight 4 level 4 integrals can be represented in terms of above 16 constants, for example,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log(x+1)\log(1-x)\arctan(x)}{x} dx = -\frac{5\pi^2G}{48} + G\log^2(2) - 6\beta(4) + 8\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) \\ + 4\log(2)\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) + \frac{7\pi\zeta(3)}{128} - \frac{1}{12}\pi\log^3(2)$$

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x\text{Li}_2\left(\frac{2x}{(x+1)^2}\right)\log(x^2+1)}{x^2+1} dx = -2G^2 + \frac{3}{2}\pi G\log(2) + \pi\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) \\ + \frac{27\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{4} + \frac{109}{32}\zeta(3)\log(2) - \frac{479\pi^4}{5760} + \frac{9\log^4(2)}{32} - \frac{9}{32}\pi^2\log^2(2)$$

0.3 Examples with the Mathematica package

There are two commands in the package, MZIntegrate and MZBasis, which we now have sufficient background to use.

MZBasis: this outputs a list of complex numbers that span $V_{N,w}^1$.

```
In[74]= MZBasis[2, 5]
Out[74]= {Zeta[5], PolyLog[5, 1/2], Log[2] PolyLog[4, 1/2], pi^2 Zeta[3], Log[2]^2 Zeta[3], pi^4 Log[2], pi^2 Log[2]^3, Log[2]^5}

In[75]= MZBasis[4, 4]
Out[75]= {PolyLog[4, 1/2], i DirichletL[4, 2, 4], i Im[PolyLog[4, 1/2 + i/2]], i pi Zeta[3], Log[2] Zeta[3], -pi Im[PolyLog[3, 1/2 + i/2]],
i Im[PolyLog[3, 1/2 + i/2]] Log[2], -Catalan^2, -i Catalan pi^2, -Catalan pi Log[2], i Catalan Log[2]^2, pi^4, -i pi^3 Log[2], -pi^2 Log[2]^2, i pi Log[2]^3, Log[2]^4}

In[76]= MZBasis[3, 3]
Out[76]= {Zeta[3], i Im[PolyLog[3, 1/2 + i/(2*sqrt(3))]], -sqrt(3) pi DirichletL[3, 2, 2], i sqrt(3) DirichletL[3, 2, 2] Log[3], -i pi^3, -pi^2 Log[3], i pi Log[3]^2, Log[3]^3}

In[82]= MZBasis[8, 3] // Short
Out[82]//Short= {Zeta[3], i Im[PolyLog[3, 1/2 + i/2]], PolyLog[3, -1 + sqrt(2)], PolyLog[3, 1/sqrt(2)],
DirichletL[8, 2, 3]/sqrt(2), <<17>>, i pi Log[1 + sqrt(2)]^2, Log[2]^3, Log[2]^2 Log[1 + sqrt(2)], Log[2] Log[1 + sqrt(2)]^2, Log[1 + sqrt(2)]^3}
```

¹the precise definition of MZBasis is not this one, but for introductory purpose, we ignore this issue

MZIntegrate: it evaluates integrals of weight w and level N .²

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (**Weight 4, level 2**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{Log}[1-x] \text{Log}[1+x] \text{Log}[x] / x, \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[83]} = & -\frac{3\pi^4}{160} - \frac{1}{12}\pi^2 \text{Log}[2]^2 + \frac{\text{Log}[2]^4}{12} + 2 \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{7}{4} \text{Log}[2] \text{Zeta}[3] \\
 & (**Weight 5, level 2**) \text{MZIntegrate}[(\text{PolyLog}[2, (1+x)/2] - \text{Zeta}[2]) \text{PolyLog}[2, x] / (1-x), \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[86]} = & \frac{29\pi^4 \text{Log}[2]}{1440} + \frac{1}{24}\pi^2 \text{Log}[2]^3 + \frac{\text{Log}[2]^5}{120} + \text{Log}[2] \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2}\right] + 4 \text{PolyLog}\left[5, \frac{1}{2}\right] - \frac{13}{48}\pi^2 \text{Zeta}[3] + \frac{1}{8} \text{Log}[2]^2 \text{Zeta}[3] - \frac{29 \text{Zeta}[5]}{16} \\
 & (**Weight 6, level 2**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{Log}[1-x]^2 \text{Log}[1+x] \text{Log}[x]^2 / (1-x), \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[85]} = & \frac{709\pi^6}{60480} + \frac{41\pi^4 \text{Log}[2]^2}{3312} - \frac{79\pi^2 \text{Log}[2]^4}{1656} + \frac{43 \text{Log}[2]^6}{414} + \frac{1}{3}\pi^2 \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2}\right] + 4 \text{Log}[2]^2 \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2}\right] + 8 \text{Log}[2] \text{PolyLog}\left[5, \frac{1}{2}\right] + \\
 & \frac{80}{23} \text{PolyLog}\left[6, \frac{1}{2}\right] - \frac{1024}{23} \text{Re}\left[\text{PolyLog}\left[6, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right]\right] - \frac{35}{24}\pi^2 \text{Log}[2] \text{Zeta}[3] + \frac{7}{6} \text{Log}[2]^3 \text{Zeta}[3] + \frac{269 \text{Zeta}[3]^2}{32} + \frac{31}{8} \text{Log}[2] \text{Zeta}[5] \\
 & (**Weight 4, level 4**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{ArcTan}[x] \text{Log}[1-x] \text{Log}[x] / (1+x), \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[90]} = & -\frac{7 \text{Catalan} \pi^2}{96} + 5 \text{DirichletL}[4, 2, 4] - 6 \text{Im}\left[\text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right]\right] - \\
 & \frac{19}{256} \pi^3 \text{Log}[2] - \frac{3}{2} \text{Im}\left[\text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right]\right] \text{Log}[2] + \frac{1}{8} \text{Catalan} \text{Log}[2]^2 + \frac{1}{64} \pi \text{Log}[2]^3 + \frac{77}{256} \pi \text{Zeta}[3]
 \end{aligned}$$

It can also do integrals of other levels, but results might be foreign to many, because not many know a basis for these $V_{N,w}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{In[92]} = (**Weight 9, level 1**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{PolyLog}[3, 1-x] \text{PolyLog}[2, x]^2 \text{Log}[x] / x, \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[92]} = & \frac{271\pi^6 \text{Zeta}[3]}{7560} - 8 \text{Zeta}[3]^3 - \frac{19}{360}\pi^4 \text{Zeta}[5] + \frac{755}{48}\pi^2 \text{Zeta}[7] - \frac{12857 \text{Zeta}[9]}{72} \\
 & \text{In[93]} = (**Weight 4, level 3**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{ArcTan}[\text{Sqrt}[3] x / (2+x)] * \text{Log}[1-x] * \text{Log}[1+x+x^2] / x, \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[93]} = & -\frac{\pi^2 \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2]}{4\sqrt{3}} - \sqrt{3} \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 4] + 4 \text{Im}\left[\text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2\sqrt{3}}\right]\right] + 2 \text{Im}\left[\text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2\sqrt{3}}\right]\right] \text{Log}[3] + \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{3} \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2] \text{Log}[3]^2 - \frac{1}{36} \pi \text{Log}[3]^3 \\
 & \text{In[98]} = (**Weight 4, level 6**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{Log}[1+x+x^2] \text{Log}[1-x+x^2] \text{Log}[1-x] / (1+x), \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[98]} = & \frac{4139\pi^4}{77760} + \frac{69}{16} \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2]^2 - \frac{5}{4} \sqrt{3} \pi \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2] \text{Log}[2] + \frac{47}{72} \pi^2 \text{Log}[2]^2 + \frac{7 \text{Log}[2]^4}{18} - \frac{3}{16} \sqrt{3} \pi \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2] \text{Log}[3] - \frac{13}{24} \pi^2 \text{Log}[2] \text{Log}[3] - \text{Log}[2]^3 \text{Log}[3] + \\
 & \frac{17}{144} \pi^2 \text{Log}[3]^2 - \frac{3}{8} \text{Log}[2]^2 \text{Log}[3]^2 + \frac{25}{24} \text{Log}[2] \text{Log}[3]^3 - \frac{211 \text{Log}[3]^4}{576} + \frac{1}{48} \pi^2 \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \text{Log}[2]^2 \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right] - \frac{3}{16} \text{Log}[3]^2 \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{1}{8} \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right]^2 + \\
 & \frac{3}{4} \text{Log}[3] \text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{3}{2} \text{Log}[3] \text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{3}\right] - \frac{71}{192} \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{9}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{57}{8} \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{3}\right] - \frac{32}{3} \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{1}{2}\right] - 4 \text{PolyLog}\left[4, \frac{2}{3}\right] + \frac{19}{18} \text{Log}[3] \text{Zeta}[3] \\
 & \text{In[99]} = (**Weight 3, level 12**) \text{MZIntegrate}[\text{ArcTan}[x^3] \text{ArcTan}[x] / (1+x), \{x, 0, 1\}] \\
 \text{Out[99]} = & \frac{\text{Catalan} \pi}{6} - \frac{5\pi \text{DirichletL}[3, 2, 2]}{16\sqrt{3}} - \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{3} \text{DirichletL}[12, 4, 3] + \frac{1}{12} \pi^2 \text{Log}[2] - \frac{5 \text{Log}[2]^3}{192} - \frac{1}{24} \pi^2 \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}] - \frac{19}{192} \text{Log}[2]^2 \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}] + \\
 & \frac{25}{192} \text{Log}[2] \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}]^2 + \frac{5}{576} \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}]^3 - \frac{1}{16} \text{Log}[2] \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right] - \frac{1}{16} \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}] \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \text{Log}[2 + \sqrt{3}] \text{PolyLog}\left[2, \frac{1}{2}(-1 + \sqrt{3})\right] - \\
 & \frac{1}{12} \text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{4}\right] + \frac{1}{48} \text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{2}(2 - \sqrt{3})\right] + \frac{1}{6} \text{PolyLog}\left[3, 2 - \sqrt{3}\right] + \frac{5}{12} \text{PolyLog}\left[3, \frac{1}{2}(-1 + \sqrt{3})\right] + \frac{1}{12} \text{PolyLog}\left[3, -5 + 3\sqrt{3}\right] - \frac{47 \text{Zeta}[3]}{576}
 \end{aligned}$$

²actually it can do much more, more about this later

Chapter 1

Iterated integrals and multiple zeta values

1.1 Shuffle product

Let X be a set, $\mathbb{Q}\langle X \rangle$ be the free non-commutative polynomial algebra over \mathbb{Q} generated over X . Treating elements in X as alphabets, let X^* be the set of words over X .

Define a binary operation \sqcup on $\mathbb{Q}\langle X \rangle$ via:

$$w \sqcup 1 = 1 \sqcup w = w \quad xw \sqcup yv = x(w \sqcup yv) + y(xw \sqcup v)$$

for $w, v \in X^*, x, y \in X$. Then distribute \sqcup over addition and scalar multiplication. The shuffle product is commutative and associative.

Let $x_i \in X$, the above recursive definition can be written out directly:

$$(x_1 \cdots x_n) \sqcup (x_{n+1} \cdots x_{n+m}) = \sum_{\substack{\sigma \in S_{n+m} \\ \sigma(1) < \cdots < \sigma(n) \\ \sigma(n+1) < \cdots < \sigma(n+m)}} x_{\sigma^{-1}(1)} \cdots x_{\sigma^{-1}(n+m)} \quad (1.1.1)$$

Exercise 1.1.1. Let $X = \{a, b\}$, show that

$$(ab) \sqcup (ab) = 4aabb + 2abab \quad (ab) \sqcup (ba) = abab + 2abba + 2baab + baba$$

1.2 Iterated integrals

Let functions $f_i(t)$ defined on $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$, define

$$\int_a^b f_1(t)dt \cdots f_n(t)dt := \int_{a > x_1 > \cdots > x_n > b} f_1(x_1) \cdots f_{n-1}(x_{n-1}) f_n(x_n) dx_1 \cdots dx_{n-1} dx_n$$

When $n = 1$, this is the usual definite integral of $\int_a^b f_1(t)dt$. When $n = 0$, define its value to be 1.

The definition can be extended to manifold. Let $\gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow M$ a path on a manifold M , $\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n$ be differential 1-forms on M . Then we define,

$$\int_{\gamma} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n := \int_0^1 f_1(t)dt \cdots f_n(t)dt$$

with $\gamma^* \omega_i = f_i(t)dt$ being the pullback of ω . One checks this is independent to the parametrization of γ .

Proposition 1.2.1. *Let ω_i be 1-forms on a manifold M ,*

- *Path reversion:*

$$\int_{\gamma} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n = (-1)^n \int_{\gamma^{-1}} \omega_n \cdots \omega_1$$

where γ^{-1} is the reverse path of γ .

- *Path composition:*

$$\int_{\gamma_1 \gamma_2} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n = \sum_{r=0}^n \int_{\gamma_1} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_r \int_{\gamma_2} \omega_{r+1} \cdots \omega_n$$

where $\gamma_2(1) = \gamma_1(0)$, here $\gamma_1 \gamma_2$ means composition of two paths, first γ_2 , then γ_1 .

The following property is nothing more than the "principal of substitution" in definite integral.

Proposition 1.2.2 (Pullback of iterated integrals). *If $f : N \rightarrow M$ is a differentiable map between two manifolds N and M , ω_i be 1-form on M .*

$$\int_{f \circ \gamma} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n = \int_{\gamma} f^* \omega_1 \cdots f^* \omega_n \quad (1.2.1)$$

It is useful to treat differential 1-forms as alphabets of a noncommutative algebra, for example, we write

$$\int_{\gamma} (3\omega_1 \omega_2 \omega_3 + 4\omega_1^3) := 3 \int_{\gamma} \omega_1 \omega_2 \omega_3 + 4 \int_{\gamma} \omega_1 \omega_1 \omega_1$$

If X is a collection of 1-forms on M and γ a path on M , then we have a \mathbb{C} -linear map from $\mathbb{C}\langle X \rangle \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ by sending $w \mapsto \int_{\gamma} w$. This map is a homomorphism of shuffle:

Proposition 1.2.3. *Let ω_i be 1-forms on a manifold M ,*

$$\int_{\gamma} \omega_1 \cdots \omega_n \int_{\gamma} \omega_{n+1} \cdots \omega_{n+m} = \int_{\gamma} (\omega_1 \cdots \omega_n) \sqcup (\omega_{n+1} \cdots \omega_{n+m}) \quad (1.2.2)$$

1.3 Multiple polylogarithm

Denote the differential 1-form $dt/(t-a)$ on \mathbb{C} , as $\omega(a)$. The core objects of this section are integrals of form

$$\Omega(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \int_{1 > x_1 > x_2 > \dots > x_n > 0} \frac{dx_1}{x_1 - a_1} \frac{dx_2}{x_2 - a_2} \dots \frac{dx_n}{x_n - a_n} = \int_0^1 \omega(a_1) \dots \omega(a_n)$$

here $a_i \in \mathbb{C}$. They form the central object of our theory. One (not so trivial) observation is that the integral converges when:

- $a_i \in \mathbb{C} - (0, 1)$ and $a_1 \neq 1, a_n \neq 0$

Example 1.3.1. We calculate

$$\Omega(0, 1) = \int_{1 > x_1 > x_2 > 0} \frac{dx_1}{x_1} \frac{dx_2}{x_2 - 1} = \int_{1 > x_1 > 0} \frac{\log(1 - x_1)}{x_1} dx_1 = -\zeta(2)$$

When all $a_i = a$, we have

$$\Omega(a, \dots, a) = \frac{1}{n!} \left(\int_0^1 \frac{dx}{x - a} \right)^n$$

Exercise 1.3.2. (Duality of iterated integral) By making substitution $y_i = 1 - x_i$ in the multiple integral, prove that $\Omega(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) = (-1)^n \Omega(1 - a_n, 1 - a_{n-1}, \dots, 1 - a_1)$

Now we introduce a very general function, called *multiple polylogarithm*

$$\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_d \geq 1} \frac{x_1^{n_1} \dots x_d^{n_d}}{n_1^{s_1} \dots n_d^{s_d}}$$

In all subsequent discussion, we will restrict to the situation when s_i are positive integers, d is called the *depth* and $s_1 + \dots + s_d$ called the *weight*. The case $d = 1$ recovers the familiar polylogarithm $\text{Li}_s(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{x^n}{n^s}$.

The case when all $x_2, \dots, x_d = 1$ is called **generalized polylogarithm**:

$$\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_d \geq 1} \frac{x^{n_1}}{n_1^{s_1} \dots n_d^{s_d}}$$

Exercise 1.3.3. Show the defining series of multiple polylog converges absolutely when $|x_1| < 1, |x_1 x_2| < 1, \dots, |x_1 \dots x_d| < 1$.

We will be also interested in the case when all x_i are roots of unity.

Exercise 1.3.4. Assume all x_i are roots of unity. Show

- If $s_1 \geq 2$, then defining series of $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ converges absolutely.
- If $s_1 = 1$ and $x_1 \neq 1$, then defining series of $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ converges conditionally.

There is a crucial relation between iterated integral and multiple polylogarithm:

Theorem 1.3.5. Let $a_i = x_1^{-1} \cdots x_i^{-1}$, such that either $|a_i| < 1$ or a_i roots of unity, then as long as both sides converge, we have¹

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d) &= \int_0^1 \left(\frac{dt}{t}\right)^{s_1-1} \frac{dt}{a_1 - t} \cdots \left(\frac{dt}{t}\right)^{s_d-1} \frac{dt}{a_d - t} \\ &= (-1)^d \Omega(\{0\}^{s_1-1}, a_1, \dots, \{0\}^{s_d-1}, a_d) \end{aligned}$$

1.3.1 Colored multiple zeta values

Let N be a positive integer. When all x_i are N -th roots of unity and $(x_1, s_1) \neq (1, 1)$ (so the defining series converges), we say $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is a **colored multiple zeta value (CMZV)** of **weight** $\sum s_i$, **level** N and **depth** d . Let CMZV_n^N be the \mathbb{Q} -span of all CMZVs of level N and weight n , this is a finite dimensional vector space over \mathbb{Q} .

Example 1.3.6. The only possible CMZV of level 1 and weight 2 is $\text{Li}_2(1) = \zeta(2)$, so we have $\text{CMZV}_2^1 = \mathbb{Q}\zeta(2)$

The only possible CMZV of level 1 and weight 3 are

$$\text{Li}_3(1) = \zeta(3) \text{ and } \text{Li}_{2,1}(1, 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{H_{n-1}}{n^2} = \zeta(3)$$

here readers are encouraged to show the last equality, so we have $\text{CMZV}_3^1 = \mathbb{Q}\zeta(3)$.

From above relation between multiple polylog and iterated integral, we can see that CMZV_n^N is also

$$\text{CMZV}_n^N = \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}} \{ \Omega(a_1, \dots, a_n) \mid a_i \in \Gamma_N \cup \{0\}, a_1 \neq 1, a_n \neq 0 \}$$

Proposition 1.3.7. CMZVs form a graded algebra with respect to weight, that is,

$$\text{CMZV}_n^N \text{CMZV}_m^N \subset \text{CMZV}_{n+m}^N$$

¹the notation $\{0\}^n$ means 0 repeated n times

Proof. Let $x \in \text{CMZV}_n^N, y \in \text{CMZV}_m^N$, we need to prove $xy \in \text{CMZV}_{n+m}^N$. It suffices to assume $x = \Omega(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \int_0^1 \omega(a_1) \cdots \omega(a_n), y = \Omega(b_1, \dots, b_m) = \int_0^1 \omega(b_1) \cdots \omega(b_m)$, here $a_1 \neq 1, a_n \neq 0, b_1 \neq 1, b_m \neq 0$. Therefore

$$xy = \int_0^1 (\omega(a_1) \cdots \omega(a_n)) \sqcup (\omega(b_1) \cdots \omega(b_m))$$

now the shuffle product is a sum of terms of form $\omega(c_1) \cdots \omega(c_{n+m})$ with each $c_1 \neq 1, c_{n+m} \neq 0, c_i \in \{a_1, \dots, a_n, b_1, \dots, b_m\}$, integral of each of them is in CMZV_{n+m}^N , so $xy \in \text{CMZV}_{n+m}^N$. \square

When all $x_i = 1$, $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is known as **multiple zeta values**, denoted by $\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_d)$

$$\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_d) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_d \geq 1} \frac{1}{n_1^{s_1} \cdots n_d^{s_d}}$$

they are simply level 1 CMZVs. We will use the notation $\{s\}^n$ to denote s repeated n times, for example

$$\zeta(\{2\}^4) = \zeta(2, 2, 2, 2) \quad \zeta(3, \{1\}^2, \{2\}^3) = \zeta(3, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2)$$

When all $x_i = \pm 1$, $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(x_1, \dots, x_d)$ is known as **alternating multiple zeta values**, denoted by $\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_d)$, with a bar over s_i if corresponding $x_i = -1$. For example

$$\zeta(\bar{2}, 1, \bar{1}) = \sum_{n_1 > \dots > n_d \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^{n_1} (-1)^{n_3}}{n_1^2 n_2 n_3}$$

they are simply level 2 CMZVs.

1.4 Classical integrals to CMZVs

The goal of this section is to illustrate the basic idea of converting integrals to CMZVs. Recall our notation $dt/(t-a) = \omega(a)$. We then have

$$\log x = - \int_x^1 \frac{dx}{x} = - \int_x^1 \omega(0) \quad \log(1-x) = \int_0^x \frac{dx}{x-1} = \int_0^x \omega(1) \quad \log(1+x) = \int_0^x \frac{1}{x+1} = \int_0^x \omega(-1)$$

therefore

$$\log^a x = (-1)^a a! \int_x^1 \omega(0)^a \quad \log^b(1-x) = b! \int_0^x \omega(1)^b$$

Example 1.4.1. Consider the integral $I = \int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x)}{x-c} dx$,

$$I = (-1)^a a! b! \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \frac{dx}{x-c} \omega(1)^b = (-1)^a a! b! \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(c) \omega(1)^b$$

when $c = 0$, we have

$$I = (-1)^a a! b! \int_0^1 \omega(0)^{a+1} \omega(1)^b = (-1)^{a+b} a! b! \zeta(a+2, \{1\}^{b-1})$$

For example, $\int_0^1 \frac{\log^4 x \log^3(1-x)}{x} dx = -4! 3! \zeta(6, 1, 1)$. Another instance:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x)}{x+1} dx = (-1)^a a! b! \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(-1) \omega(1)^b = (-1)^{a+b+1} a! b! \zeta(\overline{a+1}, \bar{1}, \{1\}^{b-1})$$

Exercise 1.4.2. For positive integers a, b , show that $\zeta(a, \{1\}^b)$ can be expressed using π and $\zeta(2n+1)$.

Example 1.4.3. Consider

$$I = \frac{(-1)^a}{a! b! c!} \int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x) \log^c(1+x)}{x-d} dx$$

we have

$$\log^a x = (-1)^a a! \int_x^1 \omega(0)^a \quad \log^b(1-x) \log^c(1+x) = b! c! \int_0^x \omega(1)^b \sqcup \omega(-1)^c$$

Therefore

$$I = \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(d) (\omega(1)^b \sqcup \omega(-1)^c)$$

When $d = 0, 1, -1$, this can be converted to level 2 CMZVs. For example, when $a = b = c = 1, d = 0$,

$$I = \int_0^1 \omega(0)^2 (\omega(1) \omega(-1) + \omega(-1) \omega(1)) = \zeta(3, \bar{1}) + \zeta(\bar{3}, \bar{1})$$

when b, c is large, the shuffle product $\omega(1)^b \sqcup \omega(-1)^c$ contains many terms, for example:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{4} \int_0^1 \frac{\log x \log^2(1-x) \log^2(1+x)}{x+1} &= \zeta(\bar{2}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}) + \zeta(\bar{2}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}, 1, \bar{1}) + \\ &\zeta(\bar{2}, \bar{1}, 1, \bar{1}, 1) + \zeta(\bar{2}, 1, \bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}) + \zeta(\bar{2}, 1, \bar{1}, 1, \bar{1}) + \zeta(\bar{2}, 1, 1, \bar{1}, 1) \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.4.4. We have

$$\log(x+i) = \int_0^x \omega(-i) + \frac{\pi i}{2} \quad \log(x-i) = \int_0^x \omega(i) - \frac{\pi i}{2}$$

therefore

$$\log(1+x^2) = \int_0^x \omega(i) + \omega(-i) \quad 2i \arctan x = \int_0^x (\omega(-i) - \omega(i)) + \pi i$$

then

$$I = \frac{(-1)^a}{a!b!c!d!e!} \int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x) \log^c(1+x) \log^d(1+x^2) (2i \arctan x)^e}{x-f} dx = \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(f)^v$$

with

$$v = \omega(1)^b \sqcup \omega(-1)^c \sqcup (\omega(i) + \omega(-i))^d \sqcup (\omega(i) - \omega(-i) + \pi i)^e$$

when $f \in \Gamma_4$ or $f = 0$, we see that $I \in \text{CMZV}_{a+b+c+d+e+1}^4$. For example, when $c = d = e = 1$, $a = b = 0$, $f = i$, by denoting

$$L_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(a_1, \dots, a_d) = \text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_d}(i^{a_1}, \dots, i^{a_d})$$

we have

$$I = 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 0, 0, 3) + 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 0, 3, 1) - 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 2, 0, 1) - 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 2, 1, 3) + 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 3, 1, 0) \\ - 2L_{2,1,1,1}(3, 3, 3, 0) - i\pi L_{2,1,1}(3, 0, 3) - i\pi L_{2,1,1}(3, 2, 1) - i\pi L_{2,1,1}(3, 3, 1) - i\pi L_{2,1,1}(3, 3, 3)$$

Next we consider some examples involving the polylogarithm function. We have

$$\text{Li}_n(x) = - \int_0^x \omega(0)^{n-1} \omega(1) \quad \text{Li}_n(1-x) = (-1)^{n+1} \int_x^1 \omega(0) \omega(1)^{n-1}$$

For multiple polylogarithm, we also have $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_k}(x) = (-1)^k \int_0^1 \omega(0)^{s_1-1} \omega(1) \dots \omega(0)^{s_k-1} \omega(1)$

Example 1.4.5. We have

$$\text{Li}_n(x) = - \int_0^x \omega(0)^{n-1} \omega(1) \quad \text{Li}_n(1-x) = (-1)^{n+1} \int_x^1 \omega(0) \omega(1)^{n-1}$$

therefore

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x) \text{Li}_n(x)^c \text{Li}_m(1-x)^d}{x-A} dx = (-1)^{a+c+(m+1)d} a!b! \int_0^1 u \omega(A)^v$$

with

$$u = [\omega(0) \omega(1)^{m-1}] \sqcup^d \sqcup \omega(0)^a \quad v = [\omega(0)^{n-1} \omega(1)] \sqcup^c \sqcup \omega(1)^d$$

when $A = 0$ or 1 , $I \in \text{CMZV}^1$. One can write down similar expressions when Li_n, Li_m are replaced by generalized polylogarithm $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_k}$.

Now we briefly touch examples involving $\text{Li}_n(R(x))$ for rational function x . Recall the familiar definition $\omega(a) = dt/(t-a)$ for $a \in \mathbb{C}$, we extend this definition to all $a \in \hat{\mathbb{C}}$, the extended complex plane, by $\omega(\infty) = 0$.

Proposition 1.4.6. *Let $R(x)$ be a rational function (i.e. holomorphic map between $\hat{\mathbb{C}}$), then the pullback*

$$R^* \omega(a) = \omega(R^{-1}(a)) - \omega(R^{-1}(\infty))$$

Proof. One has to interpret the term $\omega(R^{-1}(a))$ in the following way: let the fibre $R^{-1}(a) = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \subset \hat{\mathbb{C}}$, counted with multiplicities, then $\omega(R^{-1}(a)) = \sum \omega(a_i)$. For the proof, note that $R^* \omega(a) = \frac{R'}{R-a} = \frac{(R-a)'}{R-a}$, which by partial fraction, decompose as zeroes and poles of $R - a$, i.e., as elements of $R^{-1}(a)$ and $R^{-1}(\infty)$. \square

Now consider the following manipulation:

$$\text{Li}_n(R(x)) = - \int_0^{R(x)} \omega(0)^{n-1} \omega(1) = - \int_{R \circ [0, x]} \omega(0)^{n-1} \omega(1) = - \int_0^x (R^* \omega(0))^{n-1} R^* \omega(1) \quad (1.4.1)$$

above equalities do not hold unconditionally, we won't investigate the most general condition for which it holds. Let us simply point out it holds when

- $R(0) = 0$ and
- $R(x) \neq 0$ or 1 when $0 < x < 1$.
- $|R(x)| \leq 1$ when $0 < x < 1$.

We will pursue this problem further in a later chapter.

Ignoring all other issues of 1.4.1, if one only looks at the last term, we have

$$R^* \omega(0) = \omega(R^{-1}(0)) - \omega(R^{-1}(\infty)) \quad R^* \omega(1) = \omega(R^{-1}(1)) - \omega(R^{-1}(\infty))$$

in order for integrals of involving above ω 's to be CMZVs of level N , a sufficient condition is that

$$R^{-1}(\{0, 1, \infty\}) \subset \Gamma_N \cup \{0, \infty\}$$

we call a rational function R satisfying above condition to be N -*unital*.

Example 1.4.7. Consider the 4-unital $R(x) = \frac{x(x-1)}{1+x^2}$, it satisfies above bullets. We compute

$$R^* \omega(0) = \omega(0) + \omega(1) - \omega(i) - \omega(-i) \quad R^* \omega(1) = \omega(-1) - \omega(i) - \omega(-i)$$

So for example,

$$\frac{(-1)^a}{a!b!} \int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x) \text{Li}_n(R(x))}{x-A} dx = \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(A) w$$

with

$$w = \omega(1)^b \sqcup ((\omega(0) + \omega(1) - \omega(i) - \omega(-i))^{n-1} (\omega(-1) - \omega(i) - \omega(-i)))$$

If $A = 0$ or $\in \Gamma_4$, then the integral is in CMZV^4 . The above reasoning works by replacing Li_n with generalized polylogarithm $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_k}$.

Example 1.4.8. Consider the 6-unital $R(x) = x(1-x)$, it satisfies above bullets. Let $\mu = e^{2\pi i/6}$. We compute

$$R^* \omega(0) = \omega(0) + \omega(1) \quad R^* \omega(1) = \omega(\mu) + \omega(\mu^5)$$

So for example,

$$\frac{(-1)^a}{a!b!} \int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1-x) \text{Li}_n(R(x))}{x-A} dx = \int_0^1 \omega(0)^a \omega(A) w$$

with

$$w = \omega(1)^b \sqcup (\omega(0) + \omega(1))^{n-1} (\omega(\mu) + \omega(\mu^5))$$

If $A = 0$ or $\in \Gamma_6$, then the integral is in CMZV^6 . The above reasoning works by replacing Li_n with generalized polylogarithm $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_k}$.

Exercise 1.4.9. Show that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\arctan x \arctan(x^2)}{x-A} \in \text{CMZV}_3^8$$

if A is 0 or an eighth root of unity.

Exercise 1.4.10. Show that

$$\int_0^1 \text{Li}_a(ix) \text{Li}_b(1-ix) \text{Li}_c\left(\frac{4x}{(x+1)^2}\right) \text{Li}_d\left(\frac{x^2}{1+x^2}\right) \text{Li}_e\left(\frac{x}{1+x}\right) \text{Li}_f\left(\frac{8(x^3+x)}{(x+1)^4}\right) \frac{dx}{x-A} \in \text{CMZV}_{a+b+c+d+e+f+1}^4$$

if $A = 0, \pm i$ or ± 1 .

Exercise 1.4.11. Find all degree 1 N -unital functions. Show that there are $(N+2)(N+1)N$ many of them.

Exercise 1.4.12. (a) Show that $\text{Li}_n(\frac{1}{2}) \in \text{CMZV}_n^2$.

(b) Show that $\text{Li}_n(\frac{1 \pm i}{2}) \in \text{CMZV}_n^4$. Hint: consider the antiderivative of $\int_0^1 \frac{\log^n x}{x^2 - 2x + 2} dx$, and use 1.3.

In a later section, we will see how to express a lot of $\text{Li}_n(\alpha)$ for different α as elements of CMZV_n^N , a small collection of them is listed below

Level	z
4	$\frac{1+i}{2}$
5	$\frac{1}{2}(1-\sqrt{5}), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5}-1), \frac{1}{2}(3-\sqrt{5})$
6	$\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{3}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{3}, \frac{8}{9}, \frac{1}{9}, -\frac{1}{8}, \frac{1}{6}(3+i\sqrt{3}), -\frac{i}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{1}{4}(1-i\sqrt{3})$
7	$\frac{1}{2} \csc\left(\frac{3\pi}{14}\right), \frac{1}{4} \csc^2\left(\frac{3\pi}{14}\right), \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{7}\right) \sec^2\left(\frac{\pi}{14}\right), \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{7}\right) \sec\left(\frac{3\pi}{14}\right)$
8	$\frac{1}{4}(2-\sqrt{2}), \frac{1}{2}(2-\sqrt{2}), 3-2\sqrt{2}, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{8}(4-3\sqrt{2}), 12\sqrt{2}-16, (1-\sqrt{2})i$
10	$\frac{1}{5}, \sqrt{5}-2, \frac{1}{4}(\sqrt{5}+1), 9-4\sqrt{5}, \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}, 5\sqrt{5}+11, 20\sqrt{5}-44, \frac{1}{16}(5-5\sqrt{5})$
12	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, 1-\sqrt{3}, 21-12\sqrt{3}, \frac{1}{8}(3-3\sqrt{3}), \frac{1}{24}(12-7\sqrt{3}), \frac{1}{18}(9-5\sqrt{3})$

Table 1.1: Some selected z 's for which $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}(z) \in \text{CMZV}^N$

This allows us to use $\text{Li}_n(z)$ to express elements in CMZV_w^N for higher N and w .

Chapter 2

Multiple zeta values

2.1 Shuffle and stuffle relations

We first investigate CMZVs of level 1, also called *multiple zeta values* (MZVs)¹. Recall we define, for positive integer $s_i, s_1 \geq 2$, we defined

$$\zeta(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k) = \sum_{n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_k} \frac{1}{n_1^{s_1} \dots n_k^{s_k}}$$

In context of level 1 CMZVs, it is customary to use letters x_0, x_1 defined as $x_0 = \frac{dx}{x} = \omega(0), x_1 = \frac{dx}{1-x} = -\omega(1)$, then we have

$$\zeta(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k) = \int_0^1 x_0^{s_1-1} x_1 x_0^{s_2-1} x_2 \dots x_0^{s_k-1} x_1$$

Let us denote \mathfrak{A} be the non-commutative algebra over \mathbb{C} generated by x_0, x_1 , denote $z_i = x_0^{i-1} x_1$. \mathfrak{A}^1 be subalgebra of \mathfrak{A} generated by z_1, z_2, \dots . \mathfrak{A}^0 be subalgebra of \mathfrak{A}^1 generated by words that does not start with x_1 and does not end with x_0 .

Under this setting, for $w \in \mathfrak{A}^0$, we can define $\zeta(w)$ as follows: $\zeta(x_0^{s_1-1} x_1 x_0^{s_2-1} x_2 \dots x_0^{s_k-1} x_1) = \zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k)$, then distribute it linearly to \mathfrak{A}^0 . For example,

$$\zeta(x_0 x_1 + 3x_0 x_1 x_1 - 2x_0^2 x_1^3) = \zeta(2) + 3\zeta(2, 1) - 2\zeta(3, 1, 1)$$

Recall our definition of generalized polylogarithm, for $w = x_0^{s_1-1} x_1 x_0^{s_2-1} x_1 \dots x_0^{s_k-1} x_1 \in \mathfrak{A}^1$, we define

$$\text{Li}_w(z) = \sum_{n_1 > n_2 > \dots > n_k} \frac{z^{n_1}}{n_1^{s_1} \dots n_k^{s_k}} = \int_0^1 w = \int_0^1 x_0^{s_1-1} x_1 x_0^{s_2-1} x_1 \dots x_0^{s_k-1} x_1 \quad |z| < 1$$

¹We shall use the term "CMZVs of level 1" and "MZVs" interchangeably.

when $w \in \mathfrak{A}^0 \iff s_1 \geq 2$, we have $\text{Li}_w(1) = \zeta(w)$. We can define $\text{Li}_v(z)$ for any $z \in \mathfrak{A}^1$ by extending it linearly.

Theorem 2.1.1. For $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^1, |z| < 1$, we have

$$\text{Li}_{u \sqcup v}(z) = \text{Li}_u(z) \text{Li}_v(z)$$

Proof. It follows from $\text{Li}_u(z) = \int_0^z u$ and the fact that shuffle product is an homomorphism for iterated integral. \square

When $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$, letting $z \rightarrow 1$ gives

Theorem 2.1.2 (Finite shuffle relation). For $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$,

$$\zeta(u \sqcup v) = \zeta(u)\zeta(v)$$

There is another kind of relation, called stuffle relation. We define a binary product $*$ in \mathfrak{A}^1 as follows: $u * 1 = 1 * u = u$ for all $u \in \mathfrak{A}^1$. For words u, v , define inductively

$$(z_{i_1} u) * (z_{i_2} v) = z_{i_1}(u * z_{i_2} v) + z_{i_2}(z_{i_1} u * v) + z_{i_1+i_2}(u * v)$$

then extend $*$ linearly to all of \mathfrak{A}^1 . For example, $z_1 * z_1 = 2z_1^2 + z_2$ and

$$z_1^2 * z_3 = z_1(z_1 * z_3) + z_3(z_1^2 * 1) + z_4(z_1 * 1) = z_1(z_1 z_3 + z_3 z_1 + z_4) + z_3 z_1^2 + z_4 z_1$$

This $*$, called stuffle product, is commutative and associative.

For positive integer $N \geq 1, w = z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k}$, we define the *multiple harmonic number* to be

$$H_N(w) = H_N(z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k}) = \sum_{N \geq n_1 > n_2 > \cdots > n_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1} \cdots n_k^{i_k}}$$

for example, $H_N(z_1) = H_N$ is the usual harmonic number, and $H_N(z_k) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{i^k}$. Extend the definition of H_N to all of $w \in \mathfrak{A}^1$.

Theorem 2.1.3. For $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^1, N \geq 1$, we have

$$H_N(u * v) = H_N(u)H_N(v)$$

Proof. It suffices to assume $u = z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k} = z_{i_1} w_1, v = z_{j_1} \cdots z_{j_r} = z_{j_1} w_2$. We prove it by induction on $n + m$.

$$H_N(u)H_N(v) = \sum_{N \geq n_1 > n_2 > \cdots > n_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1} \cdots n_k^{i_k}} \sum_{N \geq m_1 > m_2 > \cdots > m_r \geq 1} \frac{1}{m_1^{j_1} \cdots m_r^{j_r}}$$

split the product into three term, according to whether $n_1 > m_1, n_1 < m_1$ or $n_1 = m_1$, giving

$$\sum_{N \geq n_1} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1}} H_{N-1}(w_1) H_{N-1}(v) + \sum_{N \geq m_1} \frac{1}{m_1^{j_1}} H_{N-1}(u) H_{N-1}(w_2) + \sum_{N \geq n_0} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1+j_1}} H_{N-1}(w_1) H_{N-1}(w_2)$$

by induction hypothesis, they equal

$$\sum_{N \geq n_1} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1}} H_{N-1}(w_1 * v) + \sum_{N \geq m_1} \frac{1}{m_1^{j_1}} H_{N-1}(u * w_2) + \sum_{N \geq n_0} \frac{1}{n_1^{i_1+j_1}} H_{N-1}(w_1 * w_2)$$

so

$$H_N(u)H_N(v) = H_N(z_{i_1}(w_1 * v)) + H_N(z_{j_1}(u * w_2)) + H_N(z_{i_1+j_1}(w_1 * w_2))$$

definition of stuffle product completes the proof. \square

When $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$, letting $N \rightarrow \infty$ gives

Theorem 2.1.4 (Finite stuffle relation). *For $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$, we have*

$$\zeta(u * v) = \zeta(u)\zeta(v)$$

In both shuffle and stuffle relations, all words are required to be in \mathfrak{A}^0 . There is an addition relation taking account for words in \mathfrak{A}^1 :

Theorem 2.1.5 (Regularized shuffle, stuffle relation). *For any $w \in \mathfrak{A}^0$, we have $x_1 \sqcup w - x_1 * w \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ and ζ satisfies*

$$\zeta(x_1 \sqcup w - x_1 * w) = 0$$

Proof. We will prove this in a later chapter, using more advanced materials. \square

2.2 Solving for MZVs

Let a_n be sequence defined by $a_n = a_{n-2} + a_{n-3}$, $a_0 = 1, a_1 = 0, a_2 = 1$. Recall we denoted CMZV_n^1 to the space of level 1 CMZVs of weight n , that is,

$$\text{CMZV}_n^1 = \text{Span}_{\mathbb{Q}}\{\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k) \mid \sum s_i = n \quad s_i \geq 2\}$$

then it is a highly nontrivial result that²

$$\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_n^1 \leq a_n$$

and has been conjectured that equality actually holds. For example, $a_2 = 1$ agrees with the fact that the only MZV of weight 2 is $\zeta(2)$; $a_3 = 1$ agrees with the fact that the only MZV of weight 3 is $\zeta(3)$ and $\zeta(2, 1)$, the latter can be shown to equal $\zeta(3)$.

²we will not explain its proof, interested reader might want to consult the nice exposition of [6]

n	a_n	spanning set
2	1	π^2
3	1	$\zeta(3)$
4	1	π^4
5	2	$\zeta(5), \pi^2\zeta(3)$
6	2	$\zeta(3)^2, \pi^6$
7	3	$\zeta(7), \pi^2\zeta(5), \pi^4\zeta(3)$
8	4	$\pi^2\zeta(3)^2, \pi^8, \zeta(3)\zeta(5), \zeta(6, 2)$
9	5	$\zeta(9), \pi^2\zeta(7), \pi^4\zeta(5), \zeta(3)^3, \pi^6\zeta(3)$
10	7	$\zeta(8, 2), \pi^2\zeta(6, 2), \zeta(3)\zeta(7), \zeta(5)^2, \pi^2\zeta(3)\zeta(5), \pi^4\zeta(3)^2, \pi^{10}$
11	9	$\zeta(11), \zeta(8, 2, 1), \pi^2\zeta(9), \zeta(3)\zeta(6, 2), \pi^4\zeta(7), \zeta(3)^2\zeta(5), \pi^6\zeta(5), \pi^2\zeta(3)^3, \pi^8\zeta(3)$

There are 2^{n-2} MZVs of weight n : that is, the number of elements in $\{\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k) \mid \sum s_i = n, s_1 \geq 2\}$. We found three types of relations among these 2^{n-2} numbers: finite shuffle relation + finite stuffle relation + regularized double shuffle relation. So we have many linear equations involving MZVs. It has been conjectured³ that these three exhaust all relations between MZVs.

Given a weight n , we execute the following algorithm⁴ to "solve" all MZVs of this weight:

1. List out all 2^{n-2} MZVs of weight n .
2. For each $2 \leq i \leq n-2$, for each $u \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ of weight $n-i$, for each $v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ of weight $n-i$, compute $u \sqcup v$.
We have a relation $\zeta(u \sqcup v) = \zeta(u)\zeta(v)$.
3. For each $2 \leq i \leq n-2$, for each $u \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ of weight $n-i$, for each $v \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ of weight $n-i$, compute $u * v$.
We have a relation $\zeta(u * v) = \zeta(u)\zeta(v)$.
4. For each $w \in \mathfrak{A}^0$ of weight $n-1$, we have a relation $\zeta(x_1 * w - x_1 * w) = 0$.
5. If we assemble all equalities we obtained, the resulting linear system should have rank $2^{n-2} - a_n$. Pick out a_n MZVs which can serve as free variables, then solve the resulting linear system.

In this way, we obtain the table above, and each MZVs of given weight is a \mathbb{Q} -span of elements in RHS. For example, with the spanning set $\{\zeta(3)^2, \pi^6\}$ of weight 6, we have

$$\zeta(2, 1, 3) = \zeta(3)^2 - \frac{13\pi^6}{15120} \quad \zeta(2, 4) = \frac{5\pi^6}{2268} - \zeta(3)^2$$

³this has been verified for weight ≤ 24

⁴of course the efficiency can be improved, our purpose here is to merely illustrate how it goes

For spanning set $\{\pi^2\zeta(3)^2, \pi^8, \zeta(3)\zeta(5), \zeta(6, 2)\}$ of weight 8, we have

$$\zeta(2, 1, 4, 1) = \frac{15}{4}\zeta(6, 2) + \frac{\pi^2\zeta(3)^2}{3} - \frac{31\zeta(5)\zeta(3)}{2} + \frac{1667\pi^8}{1088640}$$

Note that the above theory predicts $\zeta(6, 2)$ is not reducible to ordinary zeta function $\zeta(s)$.

In the Mathematica package, there is command `MultiZeta`,

```
In[2] MultiZeta[{2, 4, 3}]
```

```
Out[2] 1/945\[\Pi]^6Zeta[3]-Zeta[3]^3/3-1/12\[\Pi]^4Zeta[5]+31/6\[\Pi]^2Zeta[7]-(1567Zeta[9])/36
```

```
In[3] MultiZeta[{2, 1, 1, 4}]
```

```
Out[3] -((14041\[\Pi]^8)/5443200)-15/2MultiZeta[{6, 2}]-1/3\[\Pi]^2Zeta[3]^2+24Zeta[3]Zeta[5]
```

It automatically expresses any MZV of weight ≤ 14 into a chosen spanning set, which when weight ≤ 11 are shown in above table.

Instead of looking at dimension of CMZV_n^1 , we also look at the space

$$\widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^1 := \frac{\text{CMZV}_n^1}{\sum_{1 < k < n} \text{CMZV}_{n-k}^1 \text{CMZV}_k^1}$$

they are "primitive constants", they do not arise from multiplication of lower weight constants. Dimensions of $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^1$ and $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_n^1$ determine each other (for a formula, see 2.4.1). Assuming $a_n = \dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_n^1$, we have the following "primitive constants" for weight 14:

2.3 Computational examples about MZVs

We mention two types of applications of MZVs to classical problem: definite integrals and Euler sums.

Example 2.3.1. Evaluate

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{\log x \log(1-x) \text{Li}_2(x)}{x} dx$$

We use the idea of last chapter. Note that

$$\log x = - \int_x^1 \omega(0) = - \int_x^1 x_0 \quad \log(1-x) = \int_0^x \omega(1) = - \int_0^x x_1 \quad \text{Li}_2(x) = \int_0^x x_0 x_1$$

So

$$I = \int_0^1 (-x_0)x_0(-x_1 \sqcup x_0 x_1) = \int_0^1 x_0^2(x_1 x_0 x_1 + 2x_0 x_1^2) = \zeta(3, 2) + 2\zeta(3, 1, 1)$$

since we solved MZVs of weight 5, substituting their values we have $I = \frac{\pi^2\zeta(3)}{6} - \frac{3\zeta(5)}{2}$.

n	$\dim \text{CMZV}_n^1$	$\dim \widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^1$	Primitive constants
2	1	1	π^2
3	1	1	$\zeta(3)$
4	1	0	
5	2	1	$\zeta(5)$
6	2	0	
7	3	1	$\zeta(7)$
8	4	1	$\zeta(6, 2)$
9	5	1	$\zeta(9)$
10	7	1	$\zeta(8, 2)$
11	9	2	$\zeta(11), \zeta(8, 2, 1)$
12	12	2	$\zeta(10, 2), \zeta(8, 2, 1, 1)$
13	16	3	$\zeta(9, 3, 1), \zeta(10, 2, 1), \zeta(13)$
14	21	3	$\zeta(12, 2), \zeta(10, 4), \zeta(10, 2, 1, 1)$

Table 2.1: Primitive constants of level 1

Example 2.3.2. Evaluate

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_2(x) \text{Li}_3(1-x) \log x}{1-x} dx$$

Note that

$$\log x = -\int_x^1 \frac{1}{t} dt \quad \text{Li}_2(x) = \int_0^x \frac{-\log t}{1-t} dt \quad \text{Li}_3(1-x) = \int_x^1 \frac{\log^2 t}{1-t} dt$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \int_0^1 (x_0 x_1^2 \sqcup -x_0) x_1 (x_0 x_1) = -\int_0^1 (2x_0^2 x_1^2 + x_0 x_1 x_0 x_1 + x_0 x_1^2 x_0) x_1 x_0 x_1 \\ &= -2\zeta(3, 1, 1, 2) - \zeta(2, 2, 1, 2) - \zeta(2, 1, 2, 2) \end{aligned}$$

each of 3 MZVs above are rational combination of $\{\pi^2 \zeta(5), \pi^4 \zeta(3), \zeta(7)\}$, substituting their values

we have $I = \frac{2\pi^4 \zeta(3)}{45} - \frac{11\pi^2 \zeta(5)}{4} + \frac{359\zeta(7)}{16}$.

In the Mathematica package, there is a command `MZIntegrate`,

```
In[2] MZIntegrate[PolyLog[2, x] PolyLog[3, 1 - x] Log[x]/(1 - x), {x, 0, 1}]
```

```
Out[2] 2/45 \[Pi]^4 Zeta[3] - 11/4 \[Pi]^2 Zeta[5] + (359 Zeta[7])/16
```

Above procedure is exactly what `MZIntegrate` performs under the hood.

Exercise 2.3.3. Show that each of following integrals

$$\int_0^1 \frac{(\text{Li}_2(x))^4}{x} dx \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\log x \log(1-x) \text{Li}_2(1-x) \text{Li}_3(1-x)}{1-x} dx \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_4(x) \text{Li}_4(1-x)}{x} dx$$

are of form

$$\mathbb{Q}\zeta(9) + \mathbb{Q}\zeta(7)\pi^2 + \mathbb{Q}\zeta(5)\pi^4 + \mathbb{Q}\zeta(3)^3 + \mathbb{Q}\zeta(3)\pi^6$$

cook up more examples yourself.

Now we turn to Euler sums. One immediate example is

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{H_n^{(p)}}{n^q} = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{H_{n-1}^{(p)} + 1/n^p}{n^q} = \sum_{n_1 > n_2 \geq 1} \frac{1}{n_1^q n_2^p} + \zeta(p+q) = \zeta(q, p) + \zeta(p+q)$$

We recall our definition of multiple harmonic sums:

$$H_n(z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k}) = \sum_{n \geq r_1 > \cdots > r_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{r_1^{i_1} \cdots r_k^{i_k}}$$

it satisfies

$$H_n(u * v) = H_n(u)H_n(v) \quad u, v \in \mathfrak{A}^1$$

Note that

$$\zeta(a, i_1, \dots, i_k) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{H_{n-1}(z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k})}{n^a}$$

Example 2.3.4. Evaluate

$$S = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_{n-1})^2 H_{n-1}^{(2)}}{n^2}$$

Note that

$$H_n = H_n(z_1) \quad H_n^{(2)} = H_n(z_2)$$

and

$$z_1 * z_1 * z_2 = 2z_1z_3 + 2z_2z_2 + 2z_3z_1 + 2z_1z_1z_2 + 2z_1z_2z_1 + 2z_2z_1z_1 + z_4$$

so

$$S = 2\zeta(2, 1, 3) + 2\zeta(2, 2, 2) + 2\zeta(2, 3, 1) + 2\zeta(2, 1, 1, 2) + 2\zeta(2, 1, 2, 1) + 2\zeta(2, 1, 1) + \zeta(2, 4)$$

expressing all these weight 6 MZVs into basis $\{\zeta(3)^2, \pi^6\}$ gives $S = \frac{23\pi^6}{3780} - \zeta(3)^2$.

Exercise 2.3.5. Show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_n)^3}{n^3} = \frac{31\pi^6}{5040} - \frac{5\zeta(3)^2}{2} \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{H_{n-1}(H_{n-1}^{(2)})^2}{n^2} = -\frac{\pi^4\zeta(3)}{30} + \frac{13\pi^2\zeta(5)}{12} - \frac{77\zeta(7)}{16}$$

cook up more examples yourself.

2.4 Exercises

Exercise 2.4.1. Show that

$$1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \zeta(\{2\}^n) (-1)^n t^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{t^2}{n^2}\right)$$

conclude using infinite product of sine that

$$\zeta(\{2\}^n) = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{(2n+1)!}$$

Exercise 2.4.2. (a) By treating A, B as alphabet, show that for any non-negative integer n , we have

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n (-1)^r (AB)^{n-r} \sqcup (AB)^{n+r} = 4^n (A^2 B^2)^n$$

(b) Using part (a), show that

$$\sum_{r=-n}^n (-1)^r \zeta(\{2\}^{n-r}) \zeta(\{2\}^{n+r}) = 4^n \zeta(\{3, 1\}^n)$$

hence deduces that

$$\zeta(\{3, 1\}^n) = \frac{2\pi^{4n}}{(4n+2)!}$$

Exercise 2.4.3 (Duality of MZVs). (a) Show that

$$\zeta(a_1 + 1, \{1\}^{b_1-1}, \dots, a_l + 1, \{1\}^{b_l-1}) = \zeta(b_l + 1, \{1\}^{a_l-1}, \dots, b_1 + 1, \{1\}^{a_1-1})$$

(b) Prove that $\zeta(2, \{1\}^n) = \zeta(n+2)$ and $\zeta(\{2, 1\}^n) = \zeta(\{3\}^n)$.

Exercise 2.4.4. (a) Show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} x^n \zeta(\{s\}^n) = \exp\left(\sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{(-1)^{k-1} x^k \zeta(sk)}{k}\right)$$

use this to deduce that

$$\zeta(\{2n\}^m) \in \mathbb{Q}\pi^{2nm}$$

(b) Show that, with $B(x, y)$ the Euler beta function,

$$\sum_{n \geq 0} x^n \zeta(\{\bar{1}\}^n) = \frac{2}{B(1 + \frac{x}{2}, \frac{1}{2} - \frac{x}{2})}$$

so $\zeta(\{\bar{1}\}^n)$ is in the algebra generated by $\pi^2, \log 2$ and $\zeta(2n + 1)$. Show that

$$\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}) = -\frac{\zeta(3)}{4} - \frac{1}{6} \log^3(2) + \frac{1}{12} \pi^2 \log(2)$$

For more special value of level 1 and 2 CMZVs, see [2].

Exercise 2.4.5. Show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_n)^5}{n^2} = \frac{11\pi^4 \zeta(3)}{30} + \frac{19\pi^2 \zeta(5)}{4} + \frac{2051\zeta(7)}{16}$$

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_n)^7}{n^2} = 56\zeta(3)^3 + \frac{5911\pi^6 \zeta(3)}{4536} + \frac{15907\pi^4 \zeta(5)}{720} + \frac{3287\pi^2 \zeta(7)}{24} + \frac{276341\zeta(9)}{72}$$

what about 6-th power?

Exercise 2.4.6. (a) Let $R = \oplus_{m \geq 0} R_m$ be a commutative graded algebra over a field $k = R_0$, with $h_k = \dim_k R_k < \infty$. Prove that

$$\bar{R}_m = \sum_{0 < n < m} R_n R_{m-n}$$

Let $\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} c_m t^m = \log(1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} h_m t^m) \in k[[t]]$, then

$$\dim_k R_m / \bar{R}_m = \sum_{k|m} \frac{\mu(k)}{k} c_{m/k} \tag{2.4.1}$$

where μ is the Mobius function.

(b) Now let R be graded algebra of MZVs, with $R_k = \text{CMZV}_k^1$. Assuming the conjectural formula for $\dim R_k$, use formula above to calculate several values of $\dim R_m / \bar{R}_m$ for small m , check them against table 2.2.

(c) Show that at weights 21, 31, 41, 51, the number of primitive constants are 17, 197, 2479, 33166 respectively. Therefore for large weight, almost all MZVs cannot be expressed in terms of ordinary $\zeta(n)$.

Chapter 3

Algebra of CMZVs I

The first section can be skipped through on first reading, we will treat the subject in a more complete perspective in a chapter. Proofs of several important statements are also postponed, reader who wants to see proofs immediately should consult reference such as [9], [11] and [10].

For applications to classical problems, understanding the last three sections are crucial.

3.1 Finite shuffle, stuffle relation

In this section, we outline some relations satisfied by CMZVs of level N . We denote

$$a = \frac{dx}{x} = \omega(0) \quad b_i = \frac{\mu^i}{1 - \mu^i t} = -\omega(\mu^{-i}) \quad z_{k,i} = a^{k-1} b_i \quad \mu = e^{2\pi i/N}$$

the non-commutative algebra generated by a, b_i (over \mathbb{C}) is denoted by \mathfrak{A}_N . The subalgebra of \mathfrak{A}_N generated by $z_{k,i}$ is denoted by \mathfrak{A}_N^1 . The subalgebra of \mathfrak{A}_N^1 generated by word not beginning with b_0 is denoted by \mathfrak{A}_N^0 . From 1.3.5, we have

$$\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}(\mu^{i_1}, \dots, \mu^{i_n}) = \int_0^1 z_{s_1, i_1} z_{s_2, i_1+i_2} \dots z_{s_n, i_1+\dots+i_n} \quad s_1 \geq 2 \text{ or } (s_1 = 1 \text{ and } N \nmid i_1) \quad (3.1.1)$$

here the condition are equivalent to convergence on either side.

We define a \mathbb{C} -linear map

$$\mathfrak{L} : \mathfrak{A}_N^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, w \mapsto \int_0^1 w$$

then by basic property of iterated integral, it is a homomorphism of shuffle: $\mathfrak{L}(u \sqcup v) = \mathfrak{L}(u)\mathfrak{L}(v)$ for $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$.

For $z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n} \in \mathfrak{A}_N^1$ and positive integer N , we define the generalized harmonic number:

$$H_N(z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n}) := \sum_{N \geq k_1 > \cdots > k_n \geq 1} \frac{\mu^{i_1 k_1} \cdots \mu^{i_n k_n}}{k_1^{s_1} \cdots k_n^{s_n}} \quad \text{Li}(z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n}) := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} H_N(z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n})$$

We define a binary operation $\bar{*}$ on \mathfrak{A}_N^1 , with 1 being identity, \mathbb{C} -bilinear and recursively by

$$z_{s, j} u \bar{*} z_{t, k} v = z_{s, j} (u \bar{*} z_{t, k} v) + z_{t, k} (z_{s, j} u \bar{*} v) + z_{s+t, j+k} (u \bar{*} v)$$

then we have

$$H_N(u \bar{*} v) = H_N(u) H_N(v)$$

Taking $N \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\text{Li}(u \bar{*} v) = \text{Li}(u) \text{Li}(v) \quad u, v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$$

We wish to transfer this to the function \mathbf{L} , by looking at 3.1.1, we define the linear operator ρ :

$$\rho : z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n} \mapsto z_{s_1, i_1} z_{s_2, i_1+i_2} \cdots z_{s_n, i_1+\cdots+i_n}$$

then we have $\text{Li}(w) = \mathbf{L}(\rho(w))$ for $w \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$. The $\bar{*}$ -homomorphism of Li can be transferred to \mathbf{L} by defining $u * v := \rho(\rho^{-1} u \bar{*} \rho^{-1} v)$ for $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^1$. In this way, we have $\mathbf{L}(u * v) = \mathbf{L}(u) \mathbf{L}(v)$.

Now we have defined two operations \sqcup and $*$ on \mathfrak{A}_N^1 , we have a map $\mathbf{L} : \mathfrak{A}_N^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, we can state the most elementary relations of CMZVs:

Theorem 3.1.1 (Finite shuffle, stuffle relations). *For $u, v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$, we have*

$$\mathbf{L}(u \sqcup v) = \mathbf{L}(u) \mathbf{L}(v) \quad \mathbf{L}(u * v) = \mathbf{L}(u) \mathbf{L}(v)$$

3.2 Regularization

The map \mathbf{L} in last section is defined only on \mathfrak{A}_N^0 , we wish to extend its definition to all of \mathfrak{A}_N . We recall the alphabet a, b_0, \dots, b_{N-1} defined previously, and fix a level N . We define recursively:

let $k, m, n \geq 0$ be integers, $\xi_i \in \{a, b_0, \dots, b_{N-1}\}$, $\xi_1 \neq b_0, \xi_k \neq a$, set $\xi_1 \cdots \xi_k a^n = \xi_1 \cdots \xi_k a^n$,

$$\mathbf{L}(b_0^m \xi_1 \cdots \xi_k a^n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } mn = k = 0 \\ \mathbf{L}(\xi_1 \cdots \xi_k) & \text{if } m = n = 0 \\ -\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^q \mathbf{L}(b_0^{m-1} \xi_1 \cdots \xi_i b_0 \xi_{i+1} \cdots \xi_q) & \text{if } m > 0 \\ -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{L}(\xi_1 \cdots \xi_{i-1} a \xi_{i+1} \cdots \xi_k a^{n-1}) & \text{if } m = 0, n > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.2.1)$$

Theorem 3.2.1. *Let $w \in \mathfrak{A}_N$, then there exists positive integers s_i, t_i and $a_i, b_i, c \in \mathbb{C}$ such that*

$$\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} w = \sum a_i \log^{s_i}(\alpha) + \sum b_i \log^{t_i}(1 - \beta) + c + o(1) \quad \alpha \rightarrow 0^+, \beta \rightarrow 1^- \quad (3.2.2)$$

the above method of extending \mathbf{L} will make $c = \mathbf{L}(w)$. Moreover, \mathbf{L} is a homomorphism of shuffle on \mathfrak{A}_N .

Proof. We will prove this in a later chapter, using more advanced materials. \square

We will see in later chapter there is another extension of \mathbf{L} from \mathfrak{A}^0 to \mathfrak{A}^1 which is a homomorphism of shuffle, and satisfies similar interpretation as in 3.2.2, except the integral is replaced by summation.

For example, we have $\mathbf{L}(b_0a) = -\mathbf{L}(ab_0) = -\zeta(2)$ and

$$\mathbf{L}(b_0b_0a) = -\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{L}(b_0ab_0) = -\frac{1}{2}(-2\mathbf{L}(ab_0b_0)) = \zeta(2, 1)$$

The above extension of \mathbf{L} give "regularized value" for some divergent integral. For example

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{x} dx = \int_0^1 a = \mathbf{L}(a) = 0$$

this agrees with 3.2.2, since $\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \frac{dx}{x} = \log \beta - \log \alpha$. When we want to emphasis a certain integral has been regularized, we will denote $\int_0^1 w$ to be the constant c in 3.2.2; but we shall freely use the conventional $\int_0^1 w$ even for divergent integral, in this case, we always mean the regularized value.

Example 3.2.2. Evaluate the convergent integral

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_5(x)(\zeta(3) - \text{Li}_3(x))}{1-x} dx$$

We first consider the integral from α to β , with $\alpha \rightarrow 0^+, \beta \rightarrow 1^-$, we only focus on constant c in 3.2.2.

Let level $N = 1$. First we calculate

$$I_1 = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_5(x)\zeta(3)}{1-x} dx = \zeta(3) \int_0^1 b_0a^4b_0 = \zeta(3)\mathbf{L}(b_0a^4b_0)$$

now by 3.2.1,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{L}(b_0a^4b_0) &= -\mathbf{L}(ab_0a^3b_0) - \mathbf{L}(a^2b_0a^2b_0) - \mathbf{L}(a^3b_0ab_0) - 2\mathbf{L}(a^4b_0^2) \\ &= -\zeta(2, 4) - \zeta(3, 3) - \zeta(4, 2) - 2\zeta(5, 1) = \frac{\zeta(3)^2}{2} - \frac{\pi^6}{540} \end{aligned}$$

Similar, one considers

$$I_2 = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_5(x)\text{Li}_3(x)}{1-x} = \int_0^1 b_0((a^4b_0) \sqcup (a^3b_0))$$

performing same computations as above (which gets quite lengthy), one obtains,

$$I_2 = \frac{\zeta(3)^3}{3} + \frac{\pi^6 \zeta(3)}{270} + \frac{13\pi^4 \zeta(5)}{90} - \frac{9\pi^2 \zeta(7)}{2} + \frac{559\zeta(9)}{24}$$

so the original convergent integral equals $I = \zeta(3)\left(\frac{\zeta(3)^2}{2} - \frac{\pi^6}{540}\right) - I_2$.

Regularized integrals can also be calculated by `MZIntegrate`: for I_2 in above example

```
In[2] MZIntegrate[PolyLog[5,x]PolyLog[3,x]/(1-x),{x,0,1}]
```

```
Out[2] 1/270\[\Pi]^6Zeta[3]+Zeta[3]^3/3+13/90\[\Pi]^4Zeta[5]-9/2\[\Pi]^2Zeta[7]+(559 Zeta[9])/24
```

In fact, `MZIntegrate` **never checks for convergence**, it calculate straight away the regularized value.

As illustrated by the simple:

```
In[3] MZIntegrate[1/x,{x,0,1}]
```

```
Out[3] 0
```

Getting rid of this analytical subtlety of convergence is indispensable for unleashing the full power of CMZVs theory, as we will see in many of our upcoming examples.

The regularized \mathbb{L} , now with domain \mathfrak{A}_N , is also an important source of relations among CMZVs:

Theorem 3.2.3 (Regularized shuffle, stuffle relations). *For $u \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$, we have*

$$\mathbb{L}(u \sqcup b_0 - u * b_0) = 0$$

Proof. We will prove this in a later chapter, using more advanced material. □

Note that this is simply a level N version of the level 1 result quoted in previous chapter.

Exercise 3.2.4 (Finite distribution relations). Let d be a divisor of N , ξ_n be (N/d) -th roots of unity, show that

$$\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}(\xi_1, \dots, \xi_n) = d^{s_1 + \dots + s_n - n} \sum_{z_i^d = \xi_i, 1 \leq i \leq n} \text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}(z_1, \dots, z_n) \quad (3.2.3)$$

There is also a regularized version, which we will state and prove in later chapter.

3.3 Dimension of CMZV_w^N

The following result, due to Deligne and Goncharov [5], is extremely deep:

Theorem 3.3.1. *Let $D(w, N)$ be defined by*

$$1 + \sum_{w=1}^{\infty} D(w, N)t^w = \begin{cases} (1 - t^2 - t^3)^{-1} & \text{if } N = 1 \\ (1 - t - t^2)^{-1} & \text{if } N = 2 \\ (1 - at + bt^2)^{-1} & \text{if } N \geq 3 \end{cases}$$

where $a = \varphi(N)/2 + \nu(N)$, $b = \nu(N) - 1$. Here $\nu(N)$ denote number of distinct prime factors of N and φ is the Euler totient function. Then $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_w^N \leq D(w, N)$.

For $N = 1$, this reduces to the sequence a_n we defined at previous chapter for MZVs. For $N = 2$, it implies $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_n^2$ is bounded above by Fibonacci numbers. For $N = 3, 4$, we have $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_n^2 \leq 2^n$.

- For $N = 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8$, we have very convincing reason to believe the upper bound $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_w^N \leq D(w, N)$ is actually an equality.
- For $N = p^k$, $p \geq 5$ prime and $k \geq 1$, the upper bound is known to be not sharp.
- For other N , limited numerical computations indicate the upper bound seems sharp.

We define the quotient vector space

$$\widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^N := \frac{\text{CMZV}_n^N}{\sum_{1 < k < n} \text{CMZV}_{n-k}^N \text{CMZV}_k^N}$$

dimension of $\widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^N$ can be interpreted as number of "primitive constants" of this weight. Using conjectured value of $\dim_{\mathbb{Q}} \text{CMZV}_w^N$, and 2.4.1, one calculates the numbers in following table:

level \ weight	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
2	1	1	1	1	2	2	4	5	8	11
3	2	1	2	3	6	9	18	30	56	99
4	2	1	2	3	6	9	18	30	56	99
5	3	2	6	13	?					
6	3	2	5	10	24	50	120	270	$> 10^3$	
7	4	4	13	?						
8	3	3	8	18	48	116	312	810	$> 10^3$	
10	4	5	16	45	144	440	$> 10^3$			
12	4	5	16	45	144	440				

Table 3.1: The number in each cell is the conjectural dimension of $\widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^N$. Shaded cells represent levels and weights that are currently recognized by the package; for level 1, the range is weight ≤ 14 .

3.4 Level 2 CMZVs

Let \bar{a}_n be the conjectural dimension of $\widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^2$, first few values are in 3.1. Similar to the flow of level 1 case, assuming we have expressed all CMZVs of level 2 weight $\leq n - 1$ in terms a spanning set, now we execute the following algorithm to "solve" all CMZVs of weight n , $N = 2$:

1. List out all $2^2 \times 3^{n-2}$ CMZVs of weight N and level 2.
2. For each $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$, for each $u \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$ of weight $n - i$, for each $v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$ of weight $n - i$, compute $u \sqcup v$. We have a relation $\mathfrak{L}(u \sqcup v) = \mathfrak{L}(u)\mathfrak{L}(v)$.
3. For each $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$, for each $u \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$ of weight $n - i$, for each $v \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$ of weight $n - i$, compute $u \ast v$. We have a relation $\mathfrak{L}(u \ast v) = \mathfrak{L}(u)\mathfrak{L}(v)$.
4. For each $w \in \mathfrak{A}_N^0$ of weight $n - 1$, we have a relation $\mathfrak{L}(b_0 \sqcup w - b_0 \ast w) = 0$.
5. Adjoin all possible finite distribution relations. (See 3.2.3)
6. Adjoin all possible regularized distribution relations. (This will be explained in later chapter)
7. If we assemble all equalities we obtained, the resulting linear system should have rank $2^2 \times 3^{n-2} - \bar{a}_n$. Pick out \bar{a}_n elements which can serve as free variables, then solve the resulting linear system.

One can then compose the above table, as well as express any level 2 CMZVs into above spanning set after above steps.

n	$\dim \text{CMZV}_n^2$	$\dim \widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^2$	Spanning set
1	1	1	$\log 2$
2	2	1	$\pi^2, \log^2 2$
3	3	1	$\zeta(3), \pi^2 \log 2, \log^3 2$
4	5	1	$\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \zeta(3) \log(2), \pi^4, \pi^2 \log^2(2), \log^4(2)$
5	8	2	$\zeta(5), \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \log(2), \pi^2 \zeta(3), \zeta(3) \log^2(2), \pi^4 \log(2), \pi^2 \log^3(2), \log^5(2)$
6	13	2	$\text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \zeta(\bar{5}, 1), \zeta(5) \log(2), \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \log(2), \pi^2 \text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \dots$
7	21	4	$\zeta(7), \text{Li}_7\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), \zeta(\bar{5}, 1, 1), \zeta(\bar{5}, \bar{1}, 1), \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \log(2), \log(2) \zeta(\bar{5}, 1), \pi^2 \zeta(5) \dots$

Table 3.2: A spanning set of CMZV_n^2 , with primitive element highlighted in blue

CMZVs of level 2 can be found using the package by `MultiZeta` with a second argument:

```
In[2] MultiZeta[{1, 2, 1}, {-1, -1, 1}]
```

```
Out[2] -(\[Pi]^4/288)-1/24\[Pi]^2Log[2]^2+Log[2]^4/24+PolyLog[4, 1/2]-1/8Log[2]Zeta[3]
```

finds $\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{2}, 1)$. The second argument $\{-1, -1, 1\}$ indicates whether there is a bar at corresponding position. Alternatively, one can use `ColoredMZV` explained below.

The element $\zeta(\bar{5}, 1)$ can be expressed in terms of polylog Li_6 , one can replace it in above table by either

$$\Re \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1+i}{2}\right) \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{243} \text{Li}_6\left(-\frac{1}{8}\right)$$

we will explain the first possibility in next section; for second possibility, see [4]¹. Concretely, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Re \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1+i}{2}\right) &= \frac{69}{512} \zeta(\bar{5}, 1) + \frac{5 \text{Li}_6\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{64} - \frac{207 \zeta(3)^2}{4096} \\ &\quad - \frac{2139 \zeta(5) \log(2)}{8192} + \frac{44827 \pi^6}{61931520} + \frac{\log^6(2)}{11520} - \frac{5 \pi^2 \log^4(2)}{36864} + \frac{343 \pi^4 \log^2(2)}{737280} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.1)$$

The weight 7 space CMZV_7^2 , on the other hand, probably cannot be expressed using Li_n alone.

It has been conjectured that, after performing steps 1 – 6, the rank of resulting linear system indeed has rank indicated. This amounts to say that **all relations of level 2 CMZVs can be found using shuffle, stuffle and distribution.**

¹it can also be interpreted in terms of level 6 CMZVs.

3.5 Level 4 CMZVs

For level 4, one performs the same procedure at previous section. Except after step 6, in order to reach conjectural dimension, one need further adjoin so-called **non-standard relations**.

More generally, for many composite levels N , there seem to exist relations that are distinct from shuffle, stuffle or distribution, called non-standard relations. For $N = 4$, a satisfactory way to find them was discovered by Zhao [9]. Using another approach, I succeed in finding them when $N = 6, 8$ ([1]). In order to not interrupt our exposition, more about them will be described in later chapters.

Assuming we can find these non-standard relations, carrying out above procedures enables us to solve CMZVs of level 4.

n	$\dim \text{CMZV}_n^4$	$\dim \widetilde{\text{CMZV}}_n^4$	Primitive constants
1	2	1	$i\pi, \log 2$
2	4	1	iG
3	8	2	$\zeta(3), i\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right)$
4	16	3	$\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), i\beta(4), i\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right)$
5	32	6	$\zeta(5), \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right), i\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right), i\mathfrak{J}L_4(4, 1 1, 0), i\mathfrak{J}L_4(4, 1 1, 2), \mathfrak{R}L_4(3, 1, 1 0, 1, 1)$

Table 3.3: Primitive constants of CMZV_n^4 , the spanning set is found by multiplying these elements

CMZVs of level 4 can be found using the package by `ColoredMZV`. For example, `ColoredMZV[4, {1, 1, 2}, {3, 1, 2}]` expresses $L_4(1, 1, 2|3, 1, 2)$ into the above spanning set; `ColoredMZV[4, {2, 1, 1, 1}, {0, 1, 3, 1}]` expresses $L_4(2, 1, 1, 1|0, 1, 3, 1)$; `ColoredMZV[2, {3, 1, 2}, {0, 1, 1}]` is the same as `MultiZeta[{3, 1, 2}, {1, -1, -1}]` and $\zeta(3, \bar{1}, \bar{2})$.

We outline a proof of 3.4.1: since we have seen that $\text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1 \pm i}{2}\right) \in \text{CMZV}_n^4$, so RHS and LHS both belong to CMZV_6^4 , one express them as elements of spanning set then we're done (see 3.1). More generally, one has the following conjecture:

Conjecture 3.5.1. Let $n \geq 1$, then

$$\text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1+i}{2}\right) + \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1-i}{2}\right) \in \text{CMZV}_n^2$$

since we have "solved" CMZVs of level 4, weight ≤ 6 , this is true for $n \geq 6$.

Exercise 3.5.2. In 3.3, the weight 5 CMZVs $\mathfrak{R}L_4(4, 1|1, 0)$ does not appear, therefore it can be expressed as \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of other constants in the list, what is this expression? [You may use `ColoredMZV`]

Exercise 3.5.3. Use Mathematica command `FindIntegerNullVector`, express conjecturally $\text{Li}_7\left(\frac{1+i}{2}\right) + \text{Li}_7\left(\frac{1-i}{2}\right)$ as \mathbb{Q} -linear combination of spanning set of CMZV_7^2 .

A word of caution: π by our definition, is not a CMZV of level 4; rather it is $i\pi$ which is CMZV; similarly, the Catalan constant G is not, but rather iG . Pay attention to which constants in 3.3 are real or imaginary.

3.6 Level N CMZVs

There is a command `MZBasis[level, weight]` that allows users to consult the spanning set of CMZV_w^l . For example,

```
In[2] MZBasis[1,7]
```

```
Out[2] {Zeta[7], \[Pi]^2 Zeta[5], \[Pi]^4 Zeta[3]}
```

outputs the spanning set used to represent level 1 CMZVs of weight 7.

```
In[2] MZBasis[4,2]
```

```
Out[2] {I Catalan, \[Pi]^2, I \[Pi] Log[2], Log[2]^2}
```

outputs the spanning set used to represent level 4 CMZVs of weight 2. For levels and weights indicated in 3.1, numbers output by `MZBasis` are conjectured to be linearly independent over \mathbb{Q} , hence they **should be a basis, not only a spanning set**, of corresponding space.

Chapter 4

Classical applications of CMZVs of level 2 and 4

4.1 Definite integrals I

Example 4.1.1. Evaluate

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{\log(1+x) \log^2(1-x)}{x} dx$$

Note that

$$\log(1-x) = \int_0^x \omega(1) \quad \log(1+x) = \int_0^x \omega(-1)$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \int_0^1 \omega(0)(\omega(1) \sqcup \omega(1) \sqcup \omega(-1)) = 2 \int_0^1 \omega(0)(\omega(1)^2 \omega(-1) + \omega(1)\omega(-1)\omega(1) + \omega(-1)\omega(1)^2) \\ &= -2\text{Li}_{2,1,1}(1, 1, -1) - 2\text{Li}_{2,1,1}(1, -1, -1) - 2\text{Li}_{2,1,1}(-1, -1, 1) \\ &= -2\zeta(2, 1, \bar{1}) - 2\zeta(2, \bar{1}, \bar{1}) - 2\zeta(\bar{2}, \bar{1}, 1) \end{aligned}$$

express the last three CMZVs into above spanning set of CMZV_4^2 , we obtain $I = 2\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{7}{4}\zeta(3)\log(2) - \frac{\pi^4}{144} + \frac{\log^4(2)}{12} - \frac{1}{12}\pi^2\log^2(2)$.

Example 4.1.2. Evaluate

$$I = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_2(1-x) \log(x) \log(1+x)}{1+x} dx$$

Note that

$$\log x = - \int_x^1 \omega(0) \quad \log(1+x) = \int_0^x \omega(-1) \quad \text{Li}_2(1-x) = - \int_x^1 \omega(0)\omega(1)$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \int_0^1 (\omega(0) \sqcup \omega(0)\omega(1))\omega(-1)\omega(-1) = \int_0^1 2\omega(0)^2\omega(1)\omega(-1)^2 + \omega(0)\omega(1)\omega(0)\omega(-1)^2 \\ &= -2\zeta(3, \bar{1}, 1) - \zeta(2, \bar{2}, 1) \end{aligned}$$

express the last two CMZVs into above spanning set of CMZV_5^2 , we obtain $I = 12\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + 8\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\log(2) + \frac{19\pi^2\zeta(3)}{96} - \frac{479\zeta(5)}{32} + \frac{7\log^5(2)}{30} - \frac{1}{6}\pi^2\log^3(2) + \frac{49}{720}\pi^4\log(2)$.

Exercise 4.1.3. Write down several integrals of the form

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^a x \log^b(1+x) \log^c(1-x)}{x-A} dx \quad A \in \{0, 1, -1\}$$

and express them in terms of the spanning set of $\text{CMZV}_{a+b+c+1}^2$.

Exercise 4.1.4. Show that, for any A_1, \dots, A_i chosen from following

$$\begin{aligned} &\log x \quad \log(1-x) \quad \log(1+x) \quad \text{Li}_n(x) \quad \text{Li}_n(-x) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1-x}{2}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1+x}{2}\right) \\ &\text{Li}_n\left(\frac{4x}{(1+x)^2}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n(1-x^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.1)$$

the following can be expressed as CMZVs of level 2:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{A_1 \cdots A_i}{x-c} dx \quad c \in \{0, 1, -1\}$$

The same assertion also holds when Li_n is replaced by $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}$.

Exercise 4.1.5. Show that, for any A_1, \dots, A_i chosen from 4.1.1 plus the following

$$\begin{aligned} &\log(1+x^2) \quad \arctan x \quad \text{Li}_n(\pm ix) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{x}{x-i}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{2x}{x-i}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1}{1+x^2}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n(x^4) \\ &\text{Li}_n\left(\frac{8(x^3+x)}{(x+1)^4}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{1+x^2}{2}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{2x}{(1+x)^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.2)$$

the following can be expressed as CMZVs of level 4:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{A_1 \cdots A_i}{x-c} dx \quad c \in \{0, 1, -1\}$$

The same assertion also holds when Li_n is replaced by $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}$.

All integrals above can be computed via `MZIntegrate`, the algorithm is exactly the same as what we presented. Randomly write out some integrals and try yourself!

Exercise 4.1.6 (MSE 4405138). Show that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\arctan^2(x) \ln\left(\frac{x}{(1-x)^2}\right)}{x} = G^2$$

also evaluate

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\arctan^2(x) \ln\left(\frac{x}{(1-x)^2}\right)}{1+x} dx \quad \int_0^1 \frac{\arctan^2(x) \ln^2\left(\frac{x}{(1-x)^2}\right)}{x} dx$$

Consider the integral

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} x^n \log^a(2 \sin x) \log^b(2 \cos x)$$

Weierstrass substitution shows that it can be expressed as CMZV of level 4. Actually, with some work, one can prove it is of level 2, this example also features contour integration and regularization.

Example 4.1.7. Show that, for $a, b, n \geq 0$,

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} x^n \log^a(2 \sin x) \log^b(2 \cos x) dx \in \begin{cases} \text{CMZV}_{n+a+b+1}^2 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \pi \times \text{CMZV}_{n+a+b}^2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let

$$f(z) = \frac{\log^n z}{iz} \log^a\left(\frac{z-z^{-1}}{i}\right) \log^b(z+z^{-1})$$

Integrate $f(z)$ along quarter unit circle in first quadrant, integral along the arc is $I_1 =$

$\int_0^{\pi/2} (ix)^n \log^a(2 \sin x) \log^b(2 \cos x) dx$. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be small, integral from i to εi is

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= -i \int_{\varepsilon}^1 \frac{\log^n(ix)}{-x} \log^a(x+x^{-1}) \log^b(ix-ix^{-1}) dx \\ &= i \int_{\varepsilon}^1 \left(\log x + \frac{\pi}{2}i\right)^n (\log(1+x^2) - \log x)^a (\log(1-x^2) - \log x - \frac{\pi}{2}i)^b \frac{dx}{x} \\ &= \frac{i}{2} \int_{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}^1 \left(\frac{\log x}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}i\right)^a (\log(1+x) - \frac{\log x}{2})^a (\log(1-x) - \frac{\log x}{2} - \frac{\pi}{2}i)^b \frac{dx}{x} \end{aligned}$$

Integral from ε to 1 is

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= -i \int_{\varepsilon}^1 \log^n x (\log(1-x^2) - \log x + \frac{\pi}{2}i)^a (\log(1+x^2) - \log x)^b \frac{dx}{x} \\ &= -\frac{i}{2} \int_{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}^1 2^{-n} \log^n x (\log(1-x) - \frac{\log x}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2}i)^a (\log(1+x) - \frac{\log x}{2})^b dx \end{aligned}$$

Note that I_2, I_3 diverges if lower limit is 0, but their regularized value are in CMZV^2 . This divergence comes from the portion of contour: the small arc γ from εi to ε , we calculate its asymptotic modulo the term $\log \varepsilon$:

$$I_4 = \int_{\gamma} f(z) dz = \int_0^{\pi/2} (\log \varepsilon e^{i\theta})^n \log^a(-i\varepsilon e^{i\theta} + i\varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) \log^b(\varepsilon e^{i\theta} + \varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) d\theta$$

note that

$$\log(\varepsilon e^{i\theta} + \varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) = \log(1 + \varepsilon^2 e^{2i\theta}) + \log(\varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) \equiv -i\theta$$

since the first term is of $o(1)$; similarly

$$\log(-i\varepsilon e^{i\theta} + i\varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) = \log(1 - \varepsilon^2 e^{2i\theta}) + \log(i\varepsilon^{-1}e^{-i\theta}) \equiv \frac{\pi}{2}i - i\theta$$

so the constant term of I_4 modulo $\log \varepsilon$ is

$$i^{a+b+n} \int_0^{\pi/2} \theta^n (-\theta)^b \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta\right)^a d\theta$$

Now $I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4 = 0$, together with 3.2.2, implies the claim: for odd n , compare the imaginary part; for even n , compare the real part, note that real parts of I_2, I_3 all have a factor of $\pi/2$. \square

Exercise 4.1.8. Show that, for $a, b, n \geq 0$,

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} x^n \cot x \log^a(2 \sin x) \log^b(2 \cos x) dx \in \begin{cases} \text{CMZV}_{n+a+b+1}^2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ \pi \times \text{CMZV}_{n+a+b}^2 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

This exercise is inspired from MSE 4113352. See also MSE 4184763.

4.2 Euler sums

Recall our conventions defined in previous chapter: we have the commutative and associative multiplication $\bar{*}$ in \mathfrak{A}_N^1 , and

$$H_N(z_{s_1, i_1} \cdots z_{s_n, i_n}) := \sum_{N \geq k_1 > \cdots > k_n \geq 1} \frac{\mu^{i_1 k_1} \cdots \mu^{i_n k_n}}{k_1^{s_1} \cdots k_n^{s_n}}$$

it satisfies $H_N(u \bar{*} v) = H_N(u)H_N(v)$. We also denote $\widetilde{H}_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(-1)^{i-1}}{i}$.

Example 4.2.1. Evaluate the sum

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \widetilde{H}_{n-1}^2 H_{n-1}}{n}$$

We are in \mathfrak{A}_1^N with level $N = 2$.

$$\widetilde{H}_{n-1}^2 H_{n-1} = H_N(z_{1,1} \bar{*} z_{1,1} \bar{*} z_{1,0})$$

one computes the stuffle product:

$$z_{1,0} z_{2,0} + 2z_{1,1} z_{2,1} + z_{2,0} z_{1,0} + 2z_{2,1} z_{1,1} + 2z_{1,0} z_{1,1} z_{1,1} + 2z_{1,1} z_{1,0} z_{1,1} + 2z_{1,1} z_{1,1} z_{1,0} + z_{3,0}$$

Thus

$$S = \zeta(\bar{1}, 1, 2) + 2\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}) + \zeta(\bar{1}, 2, 1) + 2\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{2}, \bar{1}) + 2\zeta(\bar{1}, 1, \bar{1}, \bar{1}) + 2\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{1}, 1, \bar{1}) + 2\zeta(\bar{1}, \bar{1}, \bar{1}, 1) + \zeta(\bar{1}, 3)$$

which equals

$$-\frac{3}{8}\zeta(3)\log(2) + \frac{\pi^4}{288} + \frac{\log^4(2)}{4} + \frac{5}{24}\pi^2\log^2(2)$$

Exercise 4.2.2. Show that

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\widetilde{H}_{n-1}^{(2)} \widetilde{H}_{n-1}}{n^2}$$

equals

$$4\text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{\pi^2\zeta(3)}{8} - \frac{167\zeta(5)}{32} - \frac{7}{4}\zeta(3)\log^2(2) - \frac{1}{30}\log^5(2) + \frac{1}{18}\pi^2\log^3(2) + \frac{17}{360}\pi^4\log(2)$$

Example 4.2.3 (MSE 3715141). Show that

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\widetilde{H}_n^3 (-1)^n}{2n+1} \in i\text{CMZV}_4^4$$

Write the sum as

$$S = \sum_R \frac{(-1)^{n_1}}{2n_1+1} \frac{(-1)^{n_2}}{n_2} \frac{(-1)^{n_3}}{n_3} \frac{(-1)^{n_4}}{n_4}$$

here R is the set $\{(n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4) | n_1 \geq n_2, n_1 \geq n_3, n_1 \geq n_4\}$. Replace $2n_i$ by n_i , the region R remains unchanged. We have

$$S = \sum_R \frac{f(n_1)}{n_1} \frac{g(n_2)}{n_2} \frac{g(n_3)}{n_3} \frac{g(n_4)}{n_4}$$

here f, g are functions of period 4, with $f([1, 2, 3, 4]) = [1, 0, -1, 0]$ and $g([1, 2, 3, 4]) = [0, -1, 0, 1]$.

So $f(n) = -\frac{i}{2}i^n + \frac{i}{2}(-i)^n$, $g(n) = -\frac{1}{2}i^n - \frac{1}{2}(-i)^n$. Substituting them back to above sum, we see that S expands into 16 terms of form, with $i_k \in \mathbb{Z}/4\mathbb{Z}$,

$$\sum_R \frac{\mu^{i_1 n_1}}{n_1} \frac{\mu^{i_2 n_2}}{n_2} \frac{\mu^{i_3 n_3}}{n_3} \frac{\mu^{i_4 n_4}}{n_4} \quad \mu = e^{2\pi i/4} = i$$

Now we decompose the region R , we see each of such sums are in CMZV_4^4 , completing the proof.

After performing the above procedure, one obtain its value

$$S = \frac{\pi^2 G}{6} - 48\beta(4) + 64\mathfrak{J}\left(\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{1}{3}2\pi \log^3(2) + \frac{5}{8}\pi^3 \log(2)$$

Exercise 4.2.4. Show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\widetilde{H}_n^2 H_n}{(2n+1)^2} \in \text{CMZV}_4^5 \otimes \mathbb{Q}(i)$$

i.e. taking $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ -linear combinations instead of taking on \mathbb{Q} combinations. Also prove

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\widetilde{H}_n^{(2)} H_n (-1)^n}{3n+2} \in \text{CMZV}_6^4 \otimes \mathbb{Q}(e^{2\pi i/6})$$

4.3 Apéry-like series

Example 4.3.1. Show that

$$S = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^n \in \text{CMZV}_n^2$$

Note that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^n (1-x)^n}{x} dx = \frac{1}{n} \binom{2n}{n}$$

so

$$S = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{s-1}\left(-\frac{1}{2}x(1-x)\right)}{x} dx$$

Let $R = -\frac{1}{2}x(1-x)$, use the technique mentioned in last part of first chapter,

$$R^{-1}(0) = \{0, 1\} \quad R^{-1}(1) = \{-1, 2\} \quad R^{-1}(\infty) = \{\infty\}$$

We have

$$S = \int_0^1 \omega(0) a^{s-2} b \quad a = \omega(0) + \omega(1) \quad b = \omega(-1) + \omega(2)$$

expanding out the product, there are two types of terms: those contain only $\{\omega(0), \omega(1), \omega(-1)\}$ and those contain only $\{\omega(0), \omega(1), \omega(2)\}$. The first type obviously belongs to CMZV_2^s , the latter, by 1.3, also belongs to CMZV_2^s .

Exercise 4.3.2. (a) The above proof breaks down when $s = 1$, what is the value of the series in this case?

(b) Find out the explicit result for $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^n$ when $s \leq 4$, in terms of our spanning set of CMZV^2 .

Recall our definition of multiple harmonic sums:

$$H_n(z_{i_1} \cdots z_{i_k}) = H_n(i_1, \dots, i_k) = \sum_{n \geq r_1 > \dots > r_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{r_1^{i_1} \cdots r_k^{i_k}}$$

Example 4.3.3. Show that for $s \geq 2$ (for convergence reason),

$$S = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{4^n}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k) \in \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^2$$

Note that

$$\frac{4^n}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} = \int_0^1 \frac{(4x(1-x))^n}{x} dx \quad \text{Li}_{s-1, i_1, \dots, i_k}(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{x^n}{n^{s-1}} H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k)$$

so

$$S = \int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_{s-1, i_1, \dots, i_k}(4x(1-x))}{x} dx = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{2-x}\right) \text{Li}_{s-1, i_1, \dots, i_k}(x(2-x)) dx$$

in the last step, we break the integral at $x = 1/2$ and did some simple transformations. Let $R(x) = x(2-x)$, then similar to the previous example, we have

$$S = \int_0^1 (\omega(0) - \omega(2)) a^{s-1} b a^{i_1-1} b \dots a^{i_k-1} b \quad a = \omega(0) + \omega(2) \quad b = 2\omega(1)$$

so the integrand contains only ω at 0, 1 and 2, by 1.3, it is a level 2 CMZV.

In previous example, we derived an integral representation of $S_1 = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{4^n}{n^4 \binom{2n}{n}}$, namely $\int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{2-x}\right) \text{Li}_3(x(2-x)) dx$, we can use `MZIntegrate` to evaluate it:

```
In[2] MZIntegrate[(1/x + 1/(2 - x)) PolyLog[3, x (2 - x)], {x, 0, 1}]
```

```
Out[2] -((19 \[Pi]^4)/360) + 2/3 \[Pi]^2 Log[2]^2 + Log[2]^4/3 + 8 PolyLog[4, 1/2]
```

What about

$$S_2 = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{4^n}{n^2 \binom{2n}{n}} H_{n-1}(2, 1) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{2-x}\right) \text{Li}_{1,2,1}(x(2-x)) dx$$

There is a command `MZPolyLog` which represents generalized polylogarithm $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}$, with convention according to 2.1, so $\text{Li}_{1,2,1}(z)$ is the same as `MZPolyLog[{1, 0, 1, 1}, z]`^a, and we have S_2 equals

```
In[2] MZIntegrate[(1/x + 1/(2 - x)) MZPolyLog[{1, 0, 1, 1}, x (2 - x)], {x, 0, 1}]
```

```
Out[2] 3/2 \[Pi]^2 Zeta[3] - (31 Zeta[5])/2
```

^ausing notation in 2.1, $\text{Li}_{1,2,1}(z) = \int_0^z x_1 x_0 x_1 x_1$, reading the subscripts from left to right gives {1, 0, 1, 1}

Exercise 4.3.4. Show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{4^n}{n^2 \binom{2n}{n}} (H_n)^3 = 80 \text{Li}_5\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + 3\pi^2 \zeta(3) - \frac{155\zeta(5)}{8} - \frac{2}{3} \log^5(2) + \frac{16}{9} \pi^2 \log^3(2) + \frac{91}{36} \pi^4 \log(2)$$

In a later chapter, we will show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\binom{2n}{n}}{4^n} \frac{H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k)}{n^s}$$

is also in $\text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^2$, (see the exercise for a proof of weaker version) as well as

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \left(\frac{4^n}{\binom{2n}{n}} \right)^2 \frac{H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k)}{n^s} \in \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^4 \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(\frac{\binom{2n}{n}}{4^n} \right)^2 \frac{H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k)}{n^s} \in \frac{1}{\pi i} \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k+1}^4$$

They require methods of different nature.

4.4 Exercises

Exercise 4.4.1. Use MZIntegrate ¹, evaluate

$$\int_0^1 \log^2(1-x) \log^2 x \log^3(1+x) \frac{dx}{x}$$

Evaluate some other integrals

$$\int_0^1 \log^i(1-x) \log^j x \log^k(1+x) \frac{dx}{x}$$

with weight 7 and 8, look at the results. Convince yourself the above weight 8 one is **very special**. Why the result is so simple remains unexplained.

Exercise 4.4.2. (a) Using integration by parts, show that, for a, b, c non-negative integers, $N \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\int_0^1 x^N \log^a x \log^b(1+x) \log^c(1-x) dx \quad N + b + c \geq 0$$

is in $\sum_{k \leq a+b+c} \text{CMZV}_k^2$, i.e. a sum of CMZVs of different weight.

(b) Convince yourself similar assertion is true if \log is replaced by any term listed out in 4.1.1 or 4.1.2.

Exercise 4.4.3. Show that

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\log^n(1-x) \log^{n-1}(1+x)}{1+x} dx$$

is in the algebra generated over \mathbb{Q} by $\log 2$, π^2 and $\zeta(2m+1)$, $m \geq 1$.

Exercise 4.4.4. Let $\mu = e^{2\pi i/3}$. Show that, for any A_1, \dots, A_i chosen from following

$$\begin{aligned} & \log x \quad \log(1-x) \quad \log(1+x+x^2) \quad \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}x}{2+x}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n(x) \quad \text{Li}_n(\mu x) \quad \text{Li}_n(\mu^2 x) \\ & \text{Li}_n\left(\frac{3x}{1+x+x^2}\right) \quad \text{Li}_n\left(-\frac{3\mu x}{(\mu-x)^2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the following can be expressed as CMZVs of level 3:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{A_1 \dots A_i}{x-c} dx \quad c \in \{0, 1, \mu, \mu^2\}$$

The same assertion also holds when Li_n is replaced by $\text{Li}_{s_1, \dots, s_n}$.

¹or manually and painstakingly carry out the method detailed in worked examples

Exercise 4.4.5 (MSE 937912). Show that for $n \geq 1$,

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}_n(x)}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} dx \in i \times \text{CMZV}_{n+1}^4$$

hence evaluate it for $n = 2, 3$.

Exercise 4.4.6. Show that for $i, j, k \geq 0$,

$$\int_0^1 \log^i x \log^j(1-x) \log^k(1+x) \frac{x dx}{1+x^2} \in \text{CMZV}_{i+j+k+1}^4$$

Compute several instances for $i + j + k + 1 \leq 6$ (i.e. within the weight 4 range of 3.1), and observe that all instances, the result is actually in $\text{CMZV}_{i+j+k+1}^2$. For higher weight, one conjectures the integral is still of level 2, *this seems highly nontrivial*, note that it subsumes 3.5.1.

Exercise 4.4.7. Evaluate

$$\int_0^{\pi/4} x \cot x \log(\sin x) \log(\cos x) dx$$

Exercise 4.4.8. Show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{2^n n^2} \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \frac{2^m}{m^2} = -3\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{7\pi^4}{288} - \frac{1}{8} \log^4(2) - \frac{1}{8} \pi^2 \log^2(2)$$

and

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{2^n n} \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \frac{2^m}{m^3} = \frac{7}{8} \zeta(3) \log(2) - \frac{\pi^4}{288} + \frac{\log^4(2)}{24} - \frac{1}{24} \pi^2 \log^2(2)$$

Exercise 4.4.9. Evaluate

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_n)^2 H_n^{(2)}}{n} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{(H_n)^3}{n} \left(\frac{1-i}{2}\right)^n$$

Exercise 4.4.10. Consider the series, assuming convergent, s positive integer,

$$S = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{a^n}{n^s} A_1 \cdots A_k$$

- (a) When $A_1, \dots, A_k \in \{H_n^{(r)}, H_{2n}^{(r)}, \widetilde{H_{2n}^{(r)}}\}$, $a = 1$, show that $S \in \text{CMZV}^2$.
- (b) When $A_1, \dots, A_k \in \{H_n^{(r)}, H_{2n}^{(r)}, \widetilde{H_{2n}^{(r)}}, \widetilde{H_n^{(r)}}\}$, $a \in \{1, -1\}$, show that $S \in \text{CMZV}^4 \otimes \mathbb{Q}(i)$.
- (c) When $A_1, \dots, A_k \in \{H_n^{(r)}, H_{2n}^{(r)}, \widetilde{H_{2n}^{(r)}}, H_{4n}^{(r)}, \widetilde{H_{4n}^{(r)}}\}$, $a = 1$, show that $S \in \text{CMZV}^4 \otimes \mathbb{Q}(i)$.

In all cases, r need not be the same in different A_i .

Exercise 4.4.11. Evaluate

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} n^2 (H_n)^4 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^4$$

Exercise 4.4.12. (a) Show that, for $s \geq 1$,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}(H_{2n} - H_{n-1})}{n^s 2^n \binom{2n}{n}} \in \text{CMZV}_s^2$$

Hint: $\int_0^1 \frac{x^n(1-x)^n}{x} \log x dx = \frac{1}{n \binom{2n}{n}} (H_{n-1} - H_{2n})$

(b) Establish the evaluation

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}(H_{2n} - H_{n-1})}{n^2 2^n \binom{2n}{n}} &= -\frac{\zeta(3)}{8} - \frac{1}{6} \log^3(2) + \frac{1}{12} \pi^2 \log(2) \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}(H_{2n} - H_{n-1})}{n^3 2^n \binom{2n}{n}} &= -2\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{8} \zeta(3) \log(2) + \frac{19\pi^4}{720} - \frac{1}{24} \log^4(2) + \frac{1}{24} \pi^2 \log^2(2) \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 4.4.13. Show that, for $s \geq 1$,

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} \in \text{CMZV}_s^3$$

Exercise 4.4.14. Show that, for $s \geq 2$,

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s 2^n \binom{3n}{n}} \in \text{CMZV}_s^4$$

for $s = 3$ it equals

$$\pi G - \frac{33\zeta(3)}{16} + \frac{\log^3(2)}{6} - \frac{1}{24} \pi^2 \log(2)$$

also evaluate it for $s = 1, 2, 4, 5$. The case $s = 3, 4$ were conjectures of Browein [3].

Exercise 4.4.15.

$$S_n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{H_{2n} - H_n}{\binom{3n}{n} (2^n n^s)}$$

show that

$$S_1 = -\frac{\pi^2}{60} + \frac{3 \log^2(2)}{10} + \frac{1}{20} \pi \log(2) \quad S_2 = -\frac{\pi G}{2} + \frac{33\zeta(3)}{32} + \frac{1}{24} \pi^2 \log(2)$$

which were conjectures by Sun [8]. Show in general that $S_n \in \text{CMZV}_n^4$ for $n \geq 2$.

Exercise 4.4.16. Evaluate

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{4^n}{n \binom{2n}{n}} \left(\frac{14H_{n-1}}{n^5} + \frac{42H_{n-1}^{(2)}}{n^4} + \frac{10H_{n-1}^{(5)}}{n} + \frac{28}{n^6} \right)$$

Exercise 4.4.17. Let $s \geq 2$, by considering $\int_0^1 \frac{\text{Li}(R(x))}{x} dx$ with $R(x) = \frac{2x}{(1+x)^2}$, show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{2^n}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k) \in \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^4$$

Hence show that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{2^n}{n^3 \binom{2n}{n}} H_n = 2G^2 - \pi G \log 2 - 2\pi \left(\text{ImLi}_3\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right) \right) - \frac{\text{Li}_4\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{2} + \frac{137\pi^4}{2880} - \frac{\log^4 2}{48} + \frac{1}{48} 7\pi^2 \log^2 2$$

Exercise 4.4.18. The previous series when $s = 1$ also converges, it has a bit different nature than when $s \geq 2$.

Prove that

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{2^n}{n^s \binom{2n}{n}} H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k) \in \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^4 \otimes_{\mathbb{Q}} \mathbb{Q}(i)$$

i.e., taking $\mathbb{Q}(i)$ -linear combination.

For instance,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{2^n}{n \binom{2n}{n}} (H_n)^3 = & -6G^2 + \frac{\pi^2 G}{2} + 3\pi G \log 2 - 30\beta(4) + 10\pi \left(\text{ImLi}_3 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2} \right) \right) + 48 \text{ImLi}_4 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2} \right) - \frac{13 \text{Li}_4 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)}{2} \\ & - \frac{7\pi\zeta(3)}{4} - \frac{773\pi^4}{5760} - \frac{13}{48} \log^4 2 - \frac{1}{4} \pi \log^3 2 + \frac{1}{48} \pi^2 \log^2 2 + \frac{1}{8} 3\pi^3 \log 2 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 4.4.19. Show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^n \left(-3H_n + 2H_{2n} + \frac{2}{n} \right)}{n^2 \binom{2n}{n}} = \frac{7\zeta(3)}{4} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^n \left(6H_{2n} - 11H_n + \frac{8}{n} \right)}{n^2 \binom{2n}{n}} = 2\pi G$$

these were conjectures in [7]

Exercise 4.4.20. We mentioned that, which will be proved in a later chapter

$$S = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{\binom{2n}{n}}{4^n} \frac{H_{n-1}(i_1, \dots, i_k)}{n^s} \in \text{CMZV}_{s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^2$$

(a) Prove a weaker version: $S \in \frac{1}{\pi i} \text{CMZV}_{1+s+i_1+\dots+i_k}^4$ with the help of identity

$$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{2n}}{(1+x^2)^{2n+1}} dx = \frac{\pi}{4} 4^{-n} \binom{2n}{n}$$

(b) Show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\binom{2n}{n} (H_n^{(2)})^2}{4^n n} = -16 \text{Li}_5 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - 16 \text{Li}_4 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \log(2) + \frac{7\pi^2 \zeta(3)}{12} + \frac{93\zeta(5)}{8} - 7\zeta(3) \log^2(2) - \frac{8}{15} \log^5(2) + \frac{4}{9} \pi^2 \log^3(2)$$

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